

MARKETING, COMMUNICATION, SEMIOTICS. ENUNCIATIVE STRATEGIES OF COMPLICITY

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Introduction

The analysis of advertising enunciative strategies appears to occupy a limited and, in some respects, marginal area within the broader scope of marketing studies. All the more so if, as in our case, the strategies under consideration are almost exclusively those aiming to create a complicit addressee, one involved—more or less playfully—in the actualization of the text or embedded within the text itself through its simulacrum, the narratee.

We nevertheless believe that the marginality of the topic and the narrowness of perspective are only apparent. In fact, one of the primary goals of this thesis is precisely to identify and explain the reasons why the study of the parameters useful to constructing effective advertising communication can justifiably claim a respectable position within marketing studies.

We will devote the first part of our thesis to identifying the premises through which marketing, in recent years, has partially shifted its parameters and assigned specific tactical functions to advertising. In our discussion, we will attempt to bring out the signs of a growing inadequacy of the new parameters—adopted with considerable innovative effort by the marketing world—when confronted with a social landscape marked by strong systemic complexity and a transformation in the very characteristics of consumer behavior.

In the new social context, in fact, the act of consumption seems to take the form of an occasional and hardly predictable move, a tactical and appropriative gesture that responds to particular functions which may be traced back to that of

peripheral reduction of complexity. We will attempt to show the inadequacy of a marketing decision-making process conceived as a set of rigidly hierarchical operations, which would proceed from the identification of “market objectives” to the definition of more peripheral tactics. If the players involved are the strategies of the production world and the appropriative, elusive tactics of the consumer, then marketing, to maintain any control over the outcome of the interaction, must itself become cunning and agile; it must transform its strategic plan into a set of peripheral and dispersed tactics.

We will therefore hypothesize that advertising communication represents a privileged field in which to assess the tactical–strategic moves of the two parties involved. For marketing, knowledge of the reader’s encyclopedic competences and the ability to anticipate their tactical moves become highly relevant. Precisely with this aim, we will underline how the act of reading shows interesting analogies with the act of consumption (cf. paragraphs 1.4 and 14.1), and how advertising seems capable of acting upon the very use-value of the object being promoted.

It is on this theoretical background that our analysis of the enunciative strategies of complicity is situated. Once we have defined their characteristics, we will attempt to determine whether strategies of complicity can be considered a discriminating element between one advertising strategy and another, and how they relate tactically and strategically to argumentative processes and, more broadly, to the communicational strategy of the advertisement.

1 – THE TWO PRODUCTIONS

1.0 Premise

Starting from the late 1960s, within the field of socio-economic analysis, the term post-industrial comes into use to designate a type of society whose characteristics, as we will see, are significantly comparable to those described by the concept of social complexity.

Outlining the characteristic traits of this social configuration is worth considering, as the new paradigms that marketing has adopted in recent years seem to be motivated precisely by these traits. In fact, we will see that expressions such as post-industrial society and complex society describe a profound systemic transformation that ends up significantly affecting the very function of consumption. We will examine the positions of some authors on this topic and attempt to extract the distinctive features of the new scenario. The aim is not to provide a systematic treatment of the subject, but rather to identify new parameters that may justify, on the one hand, an entirely new approach to the study of marketing problems and, on the other hand, our own proposal for a systematic study of enunciative strategies understood as the study of target selection strategies and positioning criteria.

It is worth noting right away some of the issues that form the background and context of the present work. First and foremost is its interdisciplinary character, even though the intention remains to entrust semiotics—with its metalanguage as well as its particular analytical tools—with the role of constant reference point and

potential response to problems that have not found solutions through other approaches. This is, of course, an attempt at verification and, in some respects, a genuine experiment that may raise questions of a certain weight. We are not referring so much to discursive analysis, within which semiotics has consolidated heuristic tools, but rather to the connections that such analysis must necessarily establish with the distinct phases of a marketing process.

If the post-industrial transition outlines a scenario in which changes in the economic sphere are accompanied by equally profound political and cultural transformations, we are especially concerned with showing that this transition reverberates on the paradigms used in market studies, and that the new context consequently assigns to advertising specific, and at times novel, strategic functions. It becomes clear, then, that if the analysis of advertising discursive strategies were truly capable of accounting for the modes of target selection and product positioning—and if a direct correspondence were demonstrable between communication contract and brand image (to mention just some of the issues involved in a semiotic analysis of advertising effectiveness)—then semiotic analysis would genuinely emerge, this time, as a useful tool, at distinct levels, for the very conception of a marketing strategy.

We will therefore begin by outlining, in broad strokes, the characteristics of the society referred to as post-industrial, as they emerge from the work of authors such as Bell and Touraine.

1.1 Post-Industrial Transition and Social Complexity

The term post-industrial was first used by Touraine in 1970 (*La société post-industrielle*), although it was Bell who gave the concept those traits that are still recognized today as fundamental (Bell, 1983). Moreover, Touraine returned to the issue more recently (*Le retour de l'acteur*, 1987), enriching the debate with several observations that we will highlight in this very paragraph.

If we now wish to extract from Bell's discussion those features of the new scenario that are most significant for the perspective this analysis intends to adopt, we must underline a progressive shift from the production of goods to a service-based economy, and the emphatic emergence of the tertiary sector. Also significant is the growth of the quaternary and quinary sectors, where professions and functions tied to education, leisure, health—as well as finance and commerce—emerge as potential protagonists of the future scenario. But it is important to bear in mind that this new structure does not entail a simultaneous decline in the volume of mass consumer goods production; in fact, the post-industrial transition outlines a “society in which the volume of goods production remains very high, especially thanks to the introduction of automation processes in industry, which greatly increase individual productivity, allowing for higher production levels with a decreasing use of salaried labor” (Secondulfo, 1990, p. 22). The growth of these economic sectors will have significant consequences on the loss of centrality of social classes tied to the means of production, according to a process that cannot be interpreted solely in terms of economic labor relations.

In this regard, Touraine's position offers us a particularly interesting interpretive key. As is well known, the French sociologist holds that identifying the type of conflict typical of a societal model constitutes the necessary step toward recognizing the laws governing the functioning and transformation of the system in which the conflict takes shape. As a result of the method he adopts, Touraine places the formation and expression of class consciousness in a historical perspective and interprets the condition of the working class not only in terms of subjugation to capitalist domination but also in terms of cultural values. The worker is thus, from Touraine's perspective, the bearer—in industrial societies—of that particular cultural value known as productive labor. It becomes clear how this interpretive framework, which sees the emerging value conflict as the surface manifestation of the systemic laws of the broader social structure, legitimates the author in reading the decline of the workers' movement as the sign of a profound transformation affecting the industrial societal model itself. For the French sociologist, social classes are groups that, though engaged in mutual opposition, fundamentally share the same cultural orientations. Thus, industrialists and workers, the protagonists of the typical conflict of industrial society, are both bearers of the same value system; in fact, "both believe in progress, in deferred satisfaction, in a repressive control of sexual life; yet at the same time they fight one another for the social control of industrial culture, in order to assign different social forms to identical cultural orientations" (Touraine, 1984, *It. trans.*, p. 82).

Touraine has also identified the disappearance of passions and ideas linked to a strong value system as one of the defining features of post-industrial society: "To define ideas and political forces as expressions of groups and economic interests, of passions and social ideas, corresponds to an outdated image of

political life. There are no longer political passions, whereas, by contrast, the French Revolution of 1848 or the Soviet Revolution were periods in which all passions were political” (ibid., p. 74). This is, in many respects, a phenomenon typical of that condition Jean-François Lyotard defined as postmodern, characterized by the loss of strong values, the disappearance of “grand legitimizing narratives,” and the impossibility of grand theoretical interpretive systems (Lyotard, 1979).

This loss of values and functions, typical of the post-industrial transition, corresponds to the emergence of a set of social conflicts that affect values once largely relegated to the private sphere. Two examples are particularly significant for the themes this thesis intends to address: the conflictual relationship between humans and nature, and that—also critical, if not openly conflictual—between the individual and their search for social identity. On the other hand, the repeated interest we will show in the ecological question is not accidental; we indeed believe that this is emblematic of those new conflicts we are discussing. Touraine himself, while maintaining that the main conflict of programmed society (i.e., post-industrial society) is that which opposes large production and management apparatuses to consumers, identifies the only viable form of resistance for the new “dominated” in acting “in the name of the one thing that still escapes them [the ruling class], namely nature” (ibid., p. 178).

Later on (see §1.4 Consumption as Reading: A Silent Production), we will attempt to show how advertising strategy itself—if it is to anticipate the encyclopedic competence of the addressee—must take into account the characteristics of these new value-based conflicts. In this specific case, we refer to

the human–nature relationship, which appears inseparable from another delicate relationship: that which arises between the object of technology and the ecological system. The individual–social identity relationship, also central in the post-industrial transition scenario, represents the constant point of reference for this first part of our discussion; we will see that it is possible to interpret consumption as one of the main mechanisms for producing social identity and, consequently, for the episodic reduction of systemic complexity.

As we mentioned, it is the emergence of forms of social aggregation around new shared values—and thus the emergence of new conflicts—that leads to the growth and consolidation of genuine social groups that elude the old classifications tied to an “industrial vision” of society. It seems to us that the emergence of the ecological problem, more than any other, has brought to light the transversality of new social aggregations—aggregations marked by the sharing of so-called “post-material” values, as the hegemonic values of post-industrial society have been labeled. The issue was recently addressed by Luhmann (*Ökologische Kommunikation*, 1990), who implicitly and explicitly accuses the Greens of having failed to grasp the complex nature of contemporary social systems and of thereby contributing to an increase in that very complexity. Ecological themes must therefore meet the minimal conditions of communicability, so that the rediscovery of the “moral solution” to problems does not create only chaos. For Luhmann, in complex systems, social communicability is drastically constrained: “it is either comprehensible or it is noise” (*ibid.*, p. 98). The consequences, according to the author, are clear: either ecological awareness “aims to trigger social communication processes within the structure designed for that purpose (which includes structurally given possibilities of transforming structures),

or it produces only noise which, depending on the limits of social communication, must be eliminated or transformed into something communicable” (ibid.).

But beyond Luhmann’s extreme position, the ecological issue today presents itself—emblematically—as a problem precisely because it brings to the fore those new types of conflict we have mentioned. Whenever a particular productive reality is criticized by ecologists—or even when a company faces closure due to proven environmental pollution (a situation with recent parallels even in Italy)—we witness an inevitable fracture between opposing interests: those of workers fighting to keep their jobs and those of the environmentalist movement. These very episodes, as we said, highlight the transversality of certain opinion movements in relation to the values shared by traditional social strata.

Even the term transversality—used and overused, yet often present in recent theoretical discussions across various domains—offers us a first cue for general reflection. It is true, in fact, that what is defined as transversal can only be positioned in relation to a pre-existing, consolidated paradigmatic system that, to some degree, resists. This shows that, while it is true that some disciplines have changed or are changing their parameters, it is also true that in many cases the new positions struggle to assert themselves, to replace previous ones, or are forced to coexist with them—at times in tension, at times in dialectical relation.

Marketing too, understood as the set of disciplines that study the market, as well as the criteria for segmentation, exhibits the very characteristics we are describing. We will see in the chapters that follow that the goal of identifying groups sharing the same general consumption behavior is linked to the debate on

social complexity and the post-industrial transition. Moreover, what we will define as the methodological unease of marketing (see §1.3) seems to fall within that contemporary trend—typically “postmodern”—in which various disciplines renounce exhaustive aims and present themselves, with a kind of “modest attitude toward thought” (Dal Lago and Rovatti, 1989, p. 14), as weak disciplines, children of a weak thought.

1.2 Tactics versus Strategies. Complexity and Its Reduction

The issue of the reader’s attitude toward the growing presence of advertising in mass media remains highly topical. How does the recipient respond to this massive influx of messages? Do they accept them passively or resist them? Do they endure them reluctantly or, on the contrary, welcome them as pleasing, aesthetically engaging, useful, or even necessary communication? Some, for example, speak of “intrusiveness” as an inherent feature of the advertising medium, to the point of interpreting its evolution as a progressive “attempt to overcome this initial and prejudicial selective barrier” (Grandi, 1989, p. 65).

As we will see later (cf. §2), the strategies of complicity functionally respond to a series of strategic objectives, among which lies, implicitly, the very one of overcoming possible selective barriers. Our hypothesis is that the recipient does, in fact, offer resistance—a resistance with entirely specific goals and modalities.

In the following pages, we will attempt to identify an anthropological foundation for those selective processes that we may truly define as transversal.

And we will do so starting from two French authors who provide us—at times only implicitly—with a new meaning of transversality, as previously introduced: on one hand Michel Maffesoli, and on the other Michel de Certeau. In the latter we find particularly useful the distinction and opposition between two concepts corresponding to distinct logics and attitudes: strategies and tactics, as proposed in *L'invention du quotidien* (1980). Many concepts from De Certeau's essay will offer us tools capable of moving beyond certain outdated dichotomies and, at the same time, suggesting a general interpretive hypothesis regarding consumer behavior that accounts for the ongoing systemic transformations and assigns semiotics a central function in understanding many phenomena tied to the new scenario. We will also observe how semiotic tools, precisely due to their specificity, can address certain marketing issues that have been ignored or simply escaped sociological and psychological approaches, with which semiotics, however, does not seem to be in opposition and may, on the contrary, work in synergy.

De Certeau views consumption as a practice—a hidden *poiēsis* and producer of meaning—which stands in contrast to a centralized, “noisy and spectacular” production. Consumption is thus a practice whose underlying logic the author seeks to uncover. This sort of “secondary production” performed by the consumer follows rules organized according to tactics that are hidden within the processes of using information and goods. Tactics, by their very nature, are calculations and moves of cunning that cannot rely on “a proper place”; tactics can only occupy the space organized and manipulated by strategy, which has presented itself as the model for scientific, political, and economic rationality. The interest in De Certeau's theory—though, it should be noted, not originally addressed so directly to consumption and the production of goods as our usage might imply—lies, in our

view, in the conception of a “user,” a consumer, who is finally not passive; one who is certainly not sovereign, yet nonetheless capable of producing meaning through tactics of transversal appropriation.

The thought of the French historian does not end with the brief references just made, and we intend to return to other concepts from *L'invention du quotidien* when they prove useful for defining a framework for the phenomena that will emerge over the course of this work. For now, we wish to highlight significant points of convergence that these hypotheses share with the logics that characterize subcultural behavior (Hebdige, 1979). The practices of cut-up and bricolage, for instance, can be interpreted as “poor” tactics that silently carve out space within that imposed and controlled by the strategy of power. Tactics versus strategies, precisely. Tactics that produce unexpected and unpredictable meaning at the expense of a strategy seemingly cautious and unassailable; practices that, therefore, necessarily position themselves as deviant, often manifesting in transversal and unanticipated functionalizations of objects—objects in which, we might say, virtual usage schemes are actualized that the dominant strategy had not deliberately inscribed. We may then hypothesize that the mods, for example, “acted as bricoleurs when they used a different set of objects, placing them in a symbolic ensemble that served to cancel or distort their normal meanings” (Hebdige, 1979, lt. trans., p. 117).

But what we wish to assert is that such meaning-producing practices are not only characteristic of what are defined as “subcultures”; rather, we believe that a similar logic—one that generates symbolic shifts and resistance—generally characterizes the consumer behavior of the social actor in complex societies.

Michel Maffesoli's position appears to converge significantly with that of De Certeau and, moreover, offers us the opportunity to critically discuss the notion of "social alienation" as a post-industrial form of domination that follows that of "economic exploitation" (a position also shared—albeit with different nuances—by Touraine). Maffesoli identifies in popular behaviors—tactical behaviors, to use De Certeau's term—a constant tendency to relativize real powers as a mechanism we would define as defensive, emphasizing what for the sociologist is "the sovereignty of the social against the noisy and omnipresent power" (Maffesoli, 1979, It. trans., p. 26). "Faced with a 'theory' of alienation, naive and rather dogmatic, that sees the people as a historical subject always defrauded but potentially victorious in a continuous progression, one must acknowledge that, if we look at various human histories, this good people of which we are part has always known how to harmonize and play cunningly with such eternal alienation. Put somewhat gothically, beyond the 'deadly imposition' there is always a reappropriation (which occurs both perversely and directly), there is always a small-scale creation whose effectiveness cannot be underestimated" (ibid., p. 21).

Transversal, then, will be—according to the perspective we adopt—that "popular" attitude, that tactic of appropriation, of reading, of interpretation, with which marketing and advertising strategy must reckon. In this "game of cunning" between senders and receivers, we will not seek a winner—the party holding the power to utter the final word—since such a pursuit would be destined to fail or lead to irrelevant results.

In our view, in fact, the production of social identities through consumption, just like the effectiveness of advertising communication, is determined by an exchange and bargaining process in which the appropriative act of the consumer and the epistemic and interpretive act of the reader perform analogous functions—functions opposed to the production of the senders. We may compare, under a common framework, the strategies enacted by companies and the tactics of the consumer-reader-recipient—two practices governed by opposing and at times complementary logics and motivations. As we will see in the second chapter, devoted to the enunciative strategies of complicity, the issue is by no means alien to the horizon of semiotic interest.

Let us return to Maffesoli, who, in the passage quoted, offers a critique of the theory of “social alienation.” We know that for Touraine, post-industrial society is precisely characterized by the use of this lever as a tool of domination (Touraine, 1970). Social integration would then become, in the new socio-cultural context, a form of forced participation that necessarily passes through consumption. We believe we can read in this position of Touraine—if not an apocalyptic view—at least a somewhat negative interpretation in which the consumer is seen as a heterodirected and passive social actor. However, we must remember that the French sociologist’s position is highly nuanced. While it is true that, according to his analysis, the programmed society is characterized by a ruling class “capable of creating models of social consumption” (Touraine, 1984, It. trans., p. 178) and by a “directed class” describable as “the set of those who must conform to such models” (ibid.), it is also true that the author invites us to “beware of overly facile criticisms,” since post-industrial society, despite everything, “circulates people,

goods, and ideas much more intensely than previous societies ever did” (ibid., p. 172).

Gianni Vattimo (1989) has also recently interpreted the features of the new scenario “optimistically,” linking the postmodern condition to the growth and spread of mass communication media. This diffusion has, according to Vattimo, produced what he calls the “information society,” characterized by “a general explosion of *Weltanschauungen*, of worldviews” (Vattimo, 1989, p. 12) and by “a pluralization that seems irresistible, and that makes it impossible to conceive the world and history according to unitary perspectives” (ibid., p. 13). Implicitly—but also through direct critiques—Vattimo adopts a polemical stance toward those sociologists and philosophers known for their pessimistic forecasts regarding the political and cultural consequences of mass media development. And the principal referent can only be Adorno.

However, we cannot delve into this highly compelling and important debate here, as it goes beyond the aims of our discussion. The significant theoretical positions of authors like Adorno will be addressed only occasionally or implicitly. At the same time, we cannot avoid justifying an omission that might otherwise appear unjustifiable.

Let us return once again to the concept of “transversality” in the sense previously described. We propose the hypothesis that adopting new parameters may legitimize a kind of bracketing of the well-known opposition between apocalyptic and integrated intellectuals put forth by Eco in the 1960s (Eco, 1964). This suspension of judgment is not meant as a renunciation or an admission of the

problem's insolubility. Rather, it is simply a paradigmatic choice that renders certain aspects of the issue pertinent and not others. According to the perspective we are adopting, we may in fact consider valid the interpretation of consumption as a vehicle of socialization and participation—without that assumption implying that the consumer is a passively manipulable subject. Reversing the terms of the question—though it remains the same—we might consider consumption as an act performed by a social actor who moves according to tactical logics, in the sense that De Certeau gives the term.

The act of consumption, then, understood as a tactical and appropriative move, responds to its own specific functions, which may be traced to two main ones: that of reducing complexity and that of participating in the complexity of the system. These definitions will surely become clearer once we define the concept of social complexity. Our goal, once again, is to reinterpret the two functions of consumption using the parameters implicitly provided by De Certeau and Maffesoli. We accept as a starting point the definition of consumption as a social function fundamental to reducing social complexity because, as we have noted, it “produces social identities.” But we wish to emphasize those features of such behavior that are tactical—and thus typically “popular”—which in this case meet the need to simplify what appears complex, to discretize a continuum that would otherwise be difficult to manipulate.

It is also fundamental, from the perspective we have adopted, to take into account the interactive nature of the relationship established between the strategy inscribed in the object and the act of consumption. In other words, social identity

is the result of a double tactical–strategic production that involves both the forecasting operations of the sender and the interpretive moves of the recipient.

The reduction of complexity would then become nothing more than a tactical move, a “game of cunning,” the consumer’s only means of partially controlling a complex and elusive system of domination. This perspective is comparable to the interpretive key to consumption provided by Mary Douglas and Baron Isherwood: “Once we have relocated the individual within the network of their social obligations and reintegrated consumption into the social process, we will see that goods make an extremely positive contribution to rational life, especially with regard to metaphorical reasoning. This book argues that a rational being cannot behave rationally unless the world around them is endowed with coherence and regularity. To continue thinking rationally, the individual needs an intelligible world, and this intelligibility must be marked with visible cues” (Douglas and Isherwood, 1979, It. trans., p. 7).

According to the parameters we have introduced, we believe we can identify in the need for “coherence and regularity” and for an “intelligible” world, the very same reasons behind a form of consumption that presents itself as a tactical move aimed at reducing complexity. However, we do not feel able to fully share the view that consumption holds “extremely positive” functions. Choosing to view consumption as a defensive tactic instead highlights the “poor” and in some ways forced character of such behavior. As we have emphasized several times, the tactic lives parasitically within the space delineated by the strategy. Nevertheless, this does not diminish the significance or impact of the meaning production enacted by the consumer, who, though constrained by—and within—the complexity of the

social system in which they live, nonetheless demonstrates a significant capacity and possibility for action within that very system.

We now introduce another author whose positions, in our view, may prove highly important as a theoretical backdrop for this discussion: the German anthropologist and philosopher Arnold Gehlen. We are not primarily interested here in his concept of post-history or of “progress as routine,” which Gianni Vattimo identifies as a fundamental theoretical step in defining the postmodern (Vattimo, 1985, p. 15); rather, we focus on a thesis by Gehlen that is far from marginal within his overall work: the idea that human beings, by biological constitution, are instinctively poor and particularly lacking in organ-based equipment. From this derives the necessity of technology—and of the products, the commodities it produces, we might add—“precisely starting from the recognition of the imperfections of human organs. Indeed, we have techniques of integration that replace those abilities not possessed by our organs, techniques of intensification that enhance faculties already present in our body, and finally techniques of facilitation that lighten the work of the various organs” (Fadini, 1988, p. 159).

Gehlen’s thought enriches the theoretical framework we are outlining and, in our view, provides useful parameters—open to further exploration—for an interpretive grid of consumer behavior and functions in complex societies, with particular attention to the relationship between humans and objects. The relationship between Gehlen and Luhmann is, moreover, well known and widely discussed. “The latter probably owes his category of ‘complexity reduction’ also to that of *Entlastung*; but this cannot obscure the different attitudes the two thinkers

have toward modernity: distrustful and reserved in Gehlen, more affirmative in Luhmann” (ibid., p. 264). These two authors have thus addressed, from different angles, the same topic we are dealing with in this chapter. Both converge on the definition of an action schema that produces stabilization of the conflicts and tensions typical of complex societies. However, we will not delve into the points of convergence and divergence between the theoretical positions of these two philosophers, just as we will not undertake a systematic treatment of the problem of social complexity. We are, to borrow De Certeau’s phrase, “poachers,” proposing a partial, arbitrary, and motivated use of the authors we draw upon. And this way of proceeding—so emblematic of the appropriative tactics described by the French anthropologist and historian—is here openly declared, and considered useful if not indispensable. From the perspective we have adopted, authors such as Gehlen and Luhmann—but the same goes for Maffesoli and De Certeau himself—prove useful precisely because their individual positions, extracted from the broader context of their work, may acquire new meaning within the context we assign them. Is it not Maffesoli himself who maintains that “no ‘new worlds’ are discovered in the field of human sciences: we must content ourselves with unveiling this or that aspect of being-together”? (Maffesoli, 1990, p. 24)

In light of what we have just said, before turning to the key features of Luhmann’s social systems theory, we believe it is necessary to make some further clarifications regarding the way the term complexity will be used in this discussion.

As we will see, Luhmann’s definition of “complexity,” while highly fruitful for describing some of the defining traits of advanced contemporary societies, may nevertheless prove difficult to use unless it is detached from the author’s narrow

theoretical framework. In other words, we will use the term to describe phenomena that would not directly pertain to Luhmann's own concerns. According to our perspective, for example, the stratification of enunciators and narrators on one side, and of enunciatees and narratees on the other, can be considered one of the phenomena that highlight the effects social complexity has on advertising communication. ¹

Let us now turn to what Niklas Luhmann means by "complex society." According to the German sociologist and philosopher, advanced contemporary societies are social systems that engage with their environment in different, interrelated ways. Each social system has its own collective identity centered on autopoiesis (a concept Luhmann borrows from neurobiology), meaning centered on the expression of autonomy and distinctness from the environment. The system develops functional differentiation by constituting and specializing subsystems, as self-referential responses to environmental disturbances and stimuli. As Ardigò notes, for Luhmann each partial system develops a multiplicity of available structures and "seeks its own unity and autopoietic autonomy, which becomes specialized for a distinct function of the societal system" (Ardigò, 1990, p. 20). These are systems that are simultaneously open and closed with respect to their environments. Each system, in order to produce communication with other subsystems and to protect itself from environmental impacts, employs two different types of communicational filters. "The first is the filter by which the system precludes any direct interchange with the environment (this is autopoietic closure). The second filter serves to open up the internal differentiation of partial systems of a society (economy, law, science, politics, religion, education...)" (ibid., p. 21).

Ardigò notes that Luhmann adopted the concept of autopoiesis while omitting some essential features it has in neurobiology. The Italian sociologist refers in particular to the possibility of “interaction—even between two or more systemic organisms (each with its own autopoiesis)—that may go so far as to overcome mutual closures, or purely arbitrary contacts, through the creation *ex novo*—even outside a prior linguistic commonality—of a consensual domain among two or more organisms” (*ibid.*, p. 24).

We are not interested here in pushing further into that treatment; it will suffice to note that the closure of systemic units, as expressed in the autopoietic code described by Luhmann, is subject to well-argued and widely shared critiques. Still, we may extract from Luhmann’s own words the fundamental issues of social complexity and its reduction: “The still-unresolved problem of the Enlightenment concerns the way excessively complex sets of information can be processed” (Luhmann, 1970, p. 82) According to the author, “the complexity of the world, the frightening multiplicity of possibilities, must be brought back within a dimension that can be experienced as the expression of a particular meaning” (*ibid.*). He argues that it is not enough to understand the complexity of the world: “it must also be made accessible to lived experience and to action, and thus reduced. Every increase in the range of possibilities that can be grasped within the world is meaningless unless it is accompanied by the development of complexity reduction mechanisms of adequate effectiveness” (*ibid.*, p. 83).

We have already proposed a reading of such mechanisms of complexity reduction that is different but not entirely alien to the Luhmannian perspective. We

have, in fact, suggested interpreting consumption as an action—a tactical move that produces meaning and reduces complexity; a silent and “cunning” practice that brings the complexity of the world back to segmented and manageable dimensions.

1.3 The Methodological Unease of Marketing

We have described the characteristics of the post-industrial transition because they appear to motivate certain shifts in perspective within marketing theory, especially with regard to the fundamental issue of segmentation. We have emphasized the emergence of new forms of social aggregation that evidently escape classification based solely on sociodemographic parameters.

It seems that Livolsi, in his essay *Consumer Action as Rational Action*, effectively summarizes the ongoing paradigmatic shift in marketing studies:

“Until recently, the traditional marketing approach referred to the main socio-economic or demographic variables: social class, income, place of residence, etc., often considered in isolation. (...) Thus, some products were deemed feminine (in the sense that they were used or bought by women), others for people with medium-high incomes, and so on. These attempts were often too generic to explain the progressive segmentation of markets. It became necessary to go further. Also because, in the meantime, sociological research has shown that studies on social stratification can no longer explain certain phenomena, both in consumption and in politics. (...) People from different classes or social strata can now — unlike in the past — exhibit similar behaviors: buy the same things, frequent the same places, hold the same political views, and so on. (...) Differences now cut

across the groupings defined by socio-demographic variables: the same income level can derive from very different professions, with lifestyles and, consequently, consumption habits that are far from homogeneous.” (Livolsi, 1987, pp. 112–113)

It should be noted in passing that traditional demographic parameters have not been replaced by the new ones; rather, we observe a coexistence within the marketing field of non-homogeneous parameters, whose functions reveal themselves alternately as either competing or synergistic. The concept of segmentation, which developed in the 1950s, is continuously being redefined. However, as we have noted, the new parameters proposed from time to time are never able to fully replace those previously used. While it is now generally acknowledged that “the pyramid structure articulated into three main classes, typical of the 1950s and 1960s, no longer constitutes a valid analytical model,” and that “the current pattern of consumption model diffusion is matrix-based,” since “it lacks a hierarchical (top-down) conditioning system and models spread and project in all directions” (Sabbadin, 1990, p. 68), such acquisitions do not prevent marketing from occasionally falling back on segmentation criteria that may seem “outdated.”

We thus witness the coexistence of entirely heterogeneous parameters (even in the mathematical sense): geographical, demographic, socio-economic, psychographic, behavioral, etc. Moreover, new widely accepted criteria have emerged, such as the psychographic method and benefit segmentation.

We will not delve into the merits and limitations of individual criteria, as this is not the central theme of our analysis. However, we wish to start from the

observation of this articulated — not to say chaotic — situation in which marketing finds itself, to propose some reflections.

First of all, let us emphasize what appears quite evident: that marketing is adapting, perhaps with some difficulty, to the systemic changes we have described in previous chapters — the emergence of the tertiary and quaternary sectors, the rise of new values shared by new social aggregations, increasing systemic complexity, the shift from goods production to a service economy, the declining centrality of social classes tied to the means of production, and so on.

The second point of reflection we wish to propose is much less evident — and perhaps all the more interesting for that reason. According to the terminology we have introduced, we are faced with a situation that is at once paradoxical and stimulating. It would seem that marketing, rather than moving according to a logic we have defined as strategic, ends up resorting to peripheral and occasional tactical moves. Paradoxically, the world of production — itself part of a hypercomplex system — is adopting the very logics that characterize consumer behavior.

Indeed, it appears that marketing struggles to master the object of its analysis and is increasingly at the mercy of the consumer's elusive behavior. Confronted with tactics of sense-making that are transversal to the world of production, with unpredictable logics of appropriation and reduction of complexity, marketing is forced to constantly adjust its parameters, reduce discrepancies, and transform what was presumed to be a strategy into a set of peripheral and scattered tactics.

We find confirmation of this hypothesis in the new “bottom-up” theory proposed by none other than Al Ries and in the issues raised by Pascale Weil regarding “elusive and unfaithful targets” and “instant markets.” Similar considerations will lead us, from another angle, to argue for the necessity of adopting a syntagmatic approach to the study of consumer behavior.

Let us proceed in order. In an interview published in *Marketing Espansione*, Al Ries summarizes his theory in the following terms:

“Competitive arenas are changing at an increasingly frantic pace. How is it possible to plan long-term strategies when it is no longer possible to foresee in what environment a company will operate? (...) Bottom-up means starting from the ground level, from tactics, and only then moving toward defining strategies. The philosophy behind this approach is: before deciding where you want to go, you have to understand what you are capable of doing.” (Goj, 1990, p. 36)

Clearly, the bottom-up theory opposes the top-down model — that is, the established view that one should start with a general strategy and then take individual operational decisions that fulfill the functions assigned by the overarching strategy. This pyramidal and hierarchical conception of marketing operations is in fact present in the most recent marketing manuals, and is regarded, in a certain sense, as one of the discipline’s major theoretical achievements.

In other words, we are not seeking to diminish the importance — including its historical relevance — of considering tools such as advertising as integral parts of a marketing strategy.

We simply aim to recognize in Al Ries's position a sign of the methodological unease that seems to characterize marketing today. The need to "start from the bottom, from tactics, and only then move toward defining strategies," seems to us an implicit acknowledgment that consumption increasingly appears as a silent and transversal production of meaning; an implicit acknowledgment of a consumer who is ever less passive and increasingly able to carve out unexpected spaces for action.

Bottom-up is nothing more than an attempt to observe more closely the consumer's "game of cunning," in order to better anticipate occasional moves. And to do this — as we have already said — marketing becomes ever less strategic and increasingly tactical.

As we had anticipated, the recognition of consumption as a production of meaning through tactical logics is implicitly found in the book *Et moi, emoi* by Pascal Weil (1986), recently translated and published in Italy (1990). The theoretical premise from which the author begins, namely the emergence of the New Narcissus, can in fact be traced back to one of the main characteristics of post-industrial society, whose influence materializes "in the stimulation of narcissistic traits, to the point of suggesting a close link between post-industrial society and narcissistic personality" (Secondulfo, 1990, p.37). Secondulfo refers to the theories of Bell and Touraine, but also and above all to Lasch's essay *The Culture of Narcissism* (1981).

Weil's words are nonetheless quite eloquent regarding what we have chosen to define as the methodological unease of marketing. "The current evolution of behaviors and sensibilities, the spread of individualism and narcissism, the fragmentation of social values all represent a threat to marketing. (...) Unfortunately, the movement of individuals is less linear than it seems: not only do they obey the codes of more restricted groups, the tribes (which could constitute micro-markets), but they also participate in different social networks that only marginally overlap. In other words, what essentially characterizes individuals today is their ability to jump from one tribe to another, adopting each time the signs that distinguish it, the totems and taboos of that tribe, without seeking any logic in their different approaches, without attempting to reconcile the various affiliations." (Weil, 1986, it. trans., pp.113 and 117)

In truth, the claim that "individuals today" do not seek "any logic in their different approaches" is a hypothesis that needs to be verified. If the logic is not visible—much like makeup—it doesn't mean it's not there. The perspective we have adopted actually leads us to suspect that, behind the apparent illogicality of consumption behavior in contemporary societies, lie motivations and procedures whose interpretation is the difficult goal to be achieved. It might, however, be just a trivial question of terminology: "jumping from one tribe to another" or not "seeking any logic" are, according to the parameters we have proposed, interpretable as actions responding to an appropriative logic that escapes the "dominant strategy" and, naturally, the same interpretative frameworks employed in marketing studies. It is, of course, only a hypothesis. What we are nonetheless convinced of is that the apparent opacity of a phenomenon should not discourage its analysis. On the contrary, it seems to us that marketing can no longer avoid

focusing its attention on identifying and interpreting such hidden logics. And to achieve this goal, it may indeed need new methodological perspectives and new tools of analysis—tools capable of grasping the structure of such appropriative practices, which—as we have repeatedly stated—are producers of meaning.

It seems to us that semiotics can usefully be brought into play. Christian Pinson, vice president of the Association Française du Marketing, in the preface to the recent book by Jean-Marie Floch *Sémiotique, marketing et communication – Sous les signes, les stratégies*, referring to one of the French semiotician's studies on metro users' trajectories, highlights how "A l'étude psychologique du discours sur le trajet du métro, la sémiotique propose, en préalable, l'étude du trajet considéré comme texte (le discours du trajet) pour savoir comment et non pas seulement pourquoi les gens voyagent dans le métro. (...) Pour le sémioticien, les trajets sont un 'texte' et les différentes façons de vivre le trajet représentent différentes stratégies de valorisation de ce trajet. On voit bien ici le présupposé de cette démarche : le sujet est l'observateur de ses comportements et tend ensuite à en être le producteur." (Pinson, 1990, pp. VIII–IX)

Once again, what emerges is a consumer, a "user," whose practice is a true "secondary production" according to De Certeau's terminology. And this practice, whose study is entrusted to semiotics, truly constitutes a "threat" for marketing, as some authors implicitly or explicitly suggest? Pinson himself rhetorically poses the question: "Le consommateur... producteur de sens? N'est-ce pas déposséder le fabricant ou prestataire de services (l'énonciateur, pour le sémioticien) de son pouvoir? N'est-ce pas émettre une proposition hostile ou du moins dangereuse

pour le marketing? Certainement pas, si par marketing on entend vraiment recherche de la satisfaction du consommateur.” (p. IX)

The need to study the syntax of product use, that is, what is identified as the syntagmatic approach, is also, in our opinion, a consequence of defining consumption as secondary production.

By usage syntax we mean the set of “rules adopted to organize (syntactic principle) goods in their use, which may also function based on the overall goal of the consumer. This implies the possibility of understanding how a good may refer to more than one role within a consumption system or a particular purchasing occasion. This leads to the possibility of contrasting, at the level of marketing research, a syntagmatic approach with a paradigmatic one.” (Grandi, 1990b, p.61) The syntagmatic approach thus aims to describe the framework within which a product is inserted, so as to identify the combinatory potential of a certain object with other objects present on the market or otherwise available.

At the First International Conference on Marketing and Semiotics (1986), Trudy Kehret-Ward explicitly proposed this approach as one of the new possible directions of marketing research. Her paper focused on the fact that both “the marketing concept” and “the consumption system concept” have been emphasized in marketing texts over the last twenty years: “Both are stressed in the current edition of Kotler’s Marketing Management. But while the marketing concept is accorded a ritual obeisance, the consumption system concept is being rediscovered and made the centerpiece of strategic marketing analysis. The consumption system approach is coming to the fore because it has great promise

as a way of helping marketers think about how to respond to a changing environment. What is needed for this approach to achieve its full potential is an intuitive way of thinking about consumption systems.” (Kehret-Ward, 1987, p.219)

Kehret-Ward then summarizes the goals of syntagmatic marketing research in three points:

“1) Itemize the string of complementary products required by users of your product in order to achieve particular consumption goals.

2) Describe any rules for combining the products in use.

3) Describe any systematic differences in the combinatorial rules observed by different user segments.” (p.221)

The repercussions of this approach are predictable at different levels: segmentation and target definition, product design, promotion, advertising communication. We certainly cannot go into each of these issues here; for that, we refer to the two cited articles by Kehret-Ward and Grandi, which constitute a useful inventory of analyses that—let it be said—have yet to be fully carried out.

Instead, we focus on what the syntagmatic approach itself would presuppose and should account for in its applications. The reference is evidently to that manipulative and symbolic appropriation characteristic that many researchers—as we have already noted—attribute to the use of objects by subcultures, and which we have instead wanted to extend to consumption behavior in general. In other words, the practice of assembling, of organizing the consumption and use of goods according to a personal syntax—a practice nonetheless productive of meaning—is likely to escape the control of primary production (which in this case

we identify with the production system itself and with marketing strategies). We have repeatedly emphasized the elusive and transversal nature—so well captured by De Certeau—of the “productive” tactics that govern consumer behavior, of what the author calls the “user.”²

1.4 Consumption as Reading: A Silent Production

What we have argued so far seems to provide the premises for considering the analysis of advertising discursive strategies as a highly useful tool for marketing, and not merely as one of the many applications of semiotic methodology—applications that, due to their specificity and meticulousness, have sometimes appeared “interesting” but “rarely usable” in “concrete” situations.

On one hand, there is indeed a growing interest in the preliminary study of the mechanisms regulating individual initiatives within a broader strategy. There is even a perceived need to start precisely from these peripheral initiatives and then reconstruct the overall strategy (this is the so-called bottom-up theory previously discussed).

On the other hand, one can observe an analogy between the tactics of appropriation and meaning production enacted by the consumer and the tactics of reading employed by the receiver of advertising communication, who is, after all, the potential consumer.

It is De Certeau himself who highlights this analogy: “Reading (of image or text) seems to represent the highest point of passivity characterizing the consumer, made a voyeur (tied to the land or itinerant) in a society of spectacle. In fact, reading activity instead shows all the features of a silent production: a free path through the page, a metamorphosis of the text through the roaming eye, improvisation and expectation of meanings induced by some words, connections between written spaces, a sort of dance... He insinuates into the text the tricks of pleasure and of a reappropriation: he poaches in it, is transported by it, makes himself plural within it. Trick, metaphor, combinatorics, this production is also an invention of memory. It turns words into the openings of silent stories.” (De Certeau, 1980)

Both marketing strategy as a whole and the individual advertising discursive strategy must concern themselves with this “invention,” this productive activity of the subject, which seems to characterize both the act of consumption and the act of reading. It is immediately clear how close the connection is between De Certeau’s words and recent semiotic theories attentive to the cooperative nature of the reader’s activity and to the pragmatic aspects of language.

Umberto Eco, in the article “Notes on the Semiotics of Reception” (1986), emphasizes how in the last decade there has been “a paradigm shift compared to previous critical discussions. If, in the structuralist climate, the analysis of the text as an object with its own structural characteristics was prioritized—describable through more or less rigorous formalism—subsequently, the discussion has moved towards a pragmatics of reading.” (ibid. p. 9) Consequently, different semiotic theories “have taken as their object of investigation not so much the empirical

occurrences of reading (the object of a sociology of reception), but the function of construction—or deconstruction—of the text carried out by the act of reading, seen as the efficient and necessary condition of the very realization of the text as such.” (ibid. p. 10)

This renewed attention to the role of the addressee in the functioning of a text does not exclude, however, that analysis may employ a generative approach in some of its phases. Since we will have many occasions to return to this theoretical-methodological issue, we prefer for now to focus on those aspects of the act of reading highlighted by the semiotic discussion that show elements of analogy with the act of consumption. This relationship between reading and consumption is explicitly at the center of our interest, and the reasons are clear: we are preparing to assess the potential and usefulness of discursive analysis of advertising communication for marketing studies.

We can, for now, make a first, seemingly trivial observation: the attention paid to the addressee by the semiotic discussion is comparable to the increasing—and necessary—attention marketing pays to consumer behavior. The theoretical consequences are also similar: on the one hand, semiotics recognizes in the act of reading a relatively arbitrary and meaning-producing practice, indispensable for the actualization of the text; on the other, marketing is compelled to take very seriously the productive aspects of the act of consumption, now to be interpreted as an appropriative and personal practice performed by an active subject in the re-functionalization of available products and in the assignment of unforeseen added values to them.

Another observation concerns the tactical nature of both acts. We have defined as “tactics” those operations that occupy the space of strategy, without possessing one of their own. Just as the reader “poaches” in the page and carves out possible readings from the text, from the space not “protected” by the textual strategy, so the consumer organizes their consumption behaviors within a space that is not their own, but that of the consumption system and the strategy that governs it.

Both acts must, on the other hand, contend with the constraints imposed by the textual strategy conceived as a prediction of the other’s moves. “To organize their textual strategy, an author must refer to a set of competences (a broader notion than ‘knowledge of codes’) that provide content to the expressions they use. They must assume that the set of competences they refer to is the same one the reader refers to. Therefore, they will predict a Model Reader capable of cooperating in the textual actualization as the author had intended and of interpreting as the author generated.” (Eco, 1979, p. 55)

In the same way, marketing must assess the effectiveness of the strategy based on how much of the consumer’s moves it has managed to predict. In other words, the marketing strategy is forced to confront a consumption behavior which, in societies marked by increasing systemic complexity, takes on the characteristics described in the preceding paragraphs.

Beyond the appropriative tactics we have discussed, the marketing strategy must consider that, just as the text anticipates the reader’s moves, who is defined by the competences to which they refer, so too is the interpretive act of the

consumer toward a good or service regulated by the competences to which the interpreting subject refers.

However, if the cooperation of the reader is a necessary condition for the actualization of a text, this by no means implies that all readings are legitimate. The textual strategy operates precisely so that the reader chooses to actualize a specific reading among the possible ones. The text possesses a relevant semantic isotopy (Eco, 1990) that, so to speak, resists overly generic actualizations or “suspicious” interpretations. In other words, there are limits to interpretation, obstacles to the reader’s “roaming eye.”

This issue, only briefly mentioned here, will be systematically addressed in the following paragraphs. For now, our goal is to highlight, as previously stated, elements of analogy between the act of reading and that of consumption. Every object, in fact, differentiates itself from others by its usage program. The program appears as a hierarchized class of possible uses of the object, or rather, of hierarchized scripts in which the object can potentially be involved. A “brick,” to take a trivial example, is susceptible to entering numerous scripts, among which building a house seems the most probable, while homicide (the brick as a blunt weapon) is one of those virtual scripts whose actualization is only admissible in certain specific contexts.

We know well that the market, divided into individual merchandise areas, presents competing objects with very similar functional characteristics, whose necessary differentiations and positioning cannot be determined by use value

alone. Marketing, through its various available tools, undertakes to assign to each object added values capable of differentiating it from the competition.

Evidently, the object's virtual program resists its possible uses and interpretations in a way comparable to the resistance the textual strategy exerts against readings. In the case of an advertising campaign, a promotion, a product's design, the organization of retail space, and in all those cases where meaningful structures are created, it is marketing strategies and tactics that must predict (and anticipate) the possible user interpretations and provide isotopic brand-reading texts.

Let us now turn our attention, as a first example of analysis, to a text type—in this case, advertising communication—whose goal of product differentiation and positioning is achieved through the manipulation of its usage program. We refer to those numerous automobile advertisements that depict the product immersed in nature.⁴

Whether it is a car speeding alone through green hills or leaving its tracks in the desert sand or snow, the car is alone, and the image includes no other people or objects besides the unspoiled nature and the automobile itself. Since it is not our intention here to perform a detailed analysis, we find it unnecessary to refer to a specific commercial or advertising page; the remarkable homogeneity of this group of ads leads us to hypothesize a common underlying structure across various visual and discursive expressions. We believe we can say that the image of the single poster or the sequence of images comprising the commercial presents the minimal elements of narrative: according to the canonical schema of the tale,

we find a subject who performs a series of actions to unite with the desired object and who, to pursue this goal, relies on the help of an assistant or a magical object. Clearly, in this case, the actant-subject is the human being, the desideratum is nature, and the magical object is the automobile.

This initial observation alone would allow for several reflections on how advertising narratives re-propose the ways Western culture interprets the human-nature relationship, which is ultimately one of domination, organization, and conquest. Even the Christian tradition, in one of its readings, placed man at the center and lord of creation, authorizing and even assigning him to care for and improve the garden. Furthermore, the secularization of culture has led to resolving the human-nature relationship through a process mediated—more often guided—by the manipulative capabilities made available to humans and society by scientific and technical knowledge. The subject regains the lost nature through the objects provided by technology and ideally overcomes that “scarce endowment” described by Gehlen (see paragraph 1.3).

However, we would like to draw attention to other aspects that are far from marginal. Firstly, in the case mentioned, the advertising medium seems to aim to inscribe within the object a narrative program capable of enriching the set of scripts in which it can potentially participate. Advertising, in other words, through a valorization we would define as utopian (in Floch’s terms), provides the automobile with a symbolic surplus traceable to the modification of its inherent usage program.⁵

Secondly, it is worth noting how the advertising text takes into account the addressee's competence, according to the strategic necessity previously mentioned. In this case, the predictive outcome of the reader-consumer's interpretive moves is linked to the so-called ecological problem, or rather to the reader's competence on that subject. It is undisputed, in fact, that between the automobile and the natural environment there exists an ecological conflict that is hard to remove. We know, however, that the reader's related competences are largely determined by the logic adopted by the media in reporting events. In a system increasingly characterized by complexity, as we have repeatedly noted, the media, by breaking problems down into isolated and discrete units (and thus manipulable), operate a peripheral reduction of systemic complexity. Thus, the reader's competence, conditioned by the selective work previously carried out by mass media, is composed of isolated elements that give the impression that solving individual, specific issues can resolve the overall problem.

Faced with such fragmented competence, the advertising strategy emphasizes those aspects of the issue that are episodically actualizable. In fact, we must consider that sometimes, as in many of the advertisements in question, the environmental conflict is, so to speak, suppressed while remaining inevitably implied. As is well known, the canonical narrative schema includes, in addition to the elements already cited, the actants of sender and opponent. Now, many of the relevant advertisements do not present manifestations of these two actants. However, given that our analysis here is intentionally superficial and illustrative, we may venture a hypothesis about the two implied actors. We may suppose a situation of actantial syncretism, since the two functions appear to be contracted into the same actor. It is the same system of values and consumption that

distances the subject from nature and that, at the same time, charges the subject with the task of reconnecting with it.

It will certainly be noted that we have broadened the concept of reading and text to include all non-linguistic phenomena. If such a definition is standard in semiotics—and indeed, the quoted passage by De Certeau already explicitly referred to non-linguistic texts—we had initially focused on the narrower, more common usage of the two terms. Since both meanings of reading and text will prove useful in the following discussion, we willingly accept the double use of the terms we have mentioned.

We have thus observed one of the ways in which advertising, as a marketing strategy lever, works toward constructing identity and consequently positioning the product. Advertising can thus intervene in the object's usage program—which can then be translated into virtual, hierarchized narrative programs—by inscribing it into new narrative programs that ensure its valorization.

We also briefly examined how the advertising text predicts the encyclopedic knowledge of the reader, and how this knowledge is, in many cases, determined by the processes of pertinence carried out by the mass media. It is worth noting that, if it is true that the reader's competence includes the knowledge of the conflicting nature of the car-environment relationship, it is also true that common opinion sees the automobile as an indispensable means. The conflict, in a certain sense, shifts from the environment to the consumer, who cannot help but experience the contradiction dysphorically.

This is why we can identify a mythical function in the advertisements mentioned. These in fact perform a sort of reconciliation between values that are culturally opposed and an implicit liberation from the guilt generated by the conflict. We are evidently referring to the function of myth identified and studied by Lévi-Strauss: that of mediating value oppositions and realizing a space for nullification or attenuation of contradictions. In the case we have examined, the advertisement stages a narrative in which union with nature occurs without apparent contradictions. We can even say that the automobile is valorized not only as a helper in the union with the desideratum, but also as a mythical space in which, to use Floch's terms (1990), practical, utopian, critical, and ludic values coexist peacefully.

It is important to recall what, in the context of this paragraph, we intended to highlight: namely, the competences of the enunciatee activated in the act of reading and accounted for by the textual strategy on the one hand, and the tactical character that this same strategy assumes when it becomes a prediction of the enunciatee's interpretive moves (parts of a tactical appropriation project), on the other. Just as every linguistic text "hypothesizes its Model Reader, endowed with specific linguistic competences (knowledge of codes), intertextual (knowledge of other texts), encyclopedic and ideological competences (general knowledge and value systems)" (Violi and Manetti, 1979, p. 159), so too does marketing strategy construct a Model Consumer whose competences it hypothesizes.

1.4.1 The Pertinences of the Object

In the previous paragraphs, when we explicitly discussed advertising communication, we accepted as an initial hypothesis that the marketing strategy had assigned to the communication mix the function of differentiating the product from objects with similar use value. This is, in reality, a frequently occurring case, though by no means the rule (cf. paragraph 1.5.1). Naturally, there are cases in which production effectively intervenes on the product to modify its functional characteristics; in such cases, advertising can serve to inform the potential consumer, in the most suitable way, of the product's added features and benefits. These may involve the mere staging of pseudo-events (Attali, 1977) or pseudo-innovations; however, technological intervention on the product may effectively lead to positive changes in its perceived quality.

In some cases, the advertising medium is thus called upon to work synergistically with the changes effectively determined by production; in other cases, the communicative strategy directly intervenes on the product's use value. Advertising communication is therefore susceptible to contracting distinct strategic functions depending on the degree of market saturation, the brand's position relative to the competition, and any innovations or micro-innovations that may have modified, to some extent, the object's functional features.

We therefore believe that advertising must be considered as just one possible means for both symbolic and functional differentiation of the product from its competitors: the fact that it is frequently assigned such a function should not lead us to believe that marketing strategy cannot also successfully activate other

strategic levers suited to the task. It is well known that parameters such as price, distribution channel, design, and packaging (in addition, of course, to technological innovation, as already discussed) all contribute to the overall definition of the product and brand image.

All variables available to marketing must nonetheless reckon with consumer behavior which, as seen in the preceding paragraphs, today increasingly presents itself as a practice of meaning production. What has emerged from previous chapters is that the two practices—marketing and consumption—though operating with partially opposing intentions, intervene on the object through modalities and with effects that are quite similar: both the variables available to marketing strategy (among which advertising holds a privileged position) and the consumer’s tactical moves ultimately perform selections of pertinence. The very mix of levers employed by the advertising medium indeed generates choices of points of pertinence that strategically highlight certain features of the product at the expense of others. And, on the other hand, what we have defined as “meaning production through consumption” also exhibits all the characteristics of a pertinence-selection process.

This process, as previously emphasized, must still confront a certain type of resistance that the object’s functional characteristics oppose to usage practices. In the negotiated interaction that is established between the “two productions” (that of consumption and that of “production” in the conventional sense), it is by no means certain that marketing cannot continue to operate “by objectives and strategies.” Insofar as the product—understood here as one of the Ps of the marketing mix—continues to be one of the strategic levers of a marketing policy,

even minimal changes in its functional characteristics may affect the isotopic markers that offer a certain type of resistance to consumption practices. If it is true, then, that “the point of view from which the pertinence of how a material object is conceived becomes evident is never imposed, of course, by the object itself,” and that such a point of view is instead “always introduced by the subject” (Prieto, 1975, Italian trans., p. 125), we cannot, at the same time, ignore the fact that the virtual usage programs characterizing the object appear hierarchized (cf. ch. 1.4.), and that the pertinence-selection process, however free, cannot be arbitrary.

What should be of fundamental importance to marketing is the social character of this process: “since the subject is always a social subject, every knowledge of material reality involves, at the very level of the identity it attributes to its object, a component—pertinence—which, being not ‘given’ (i.e., imposed by the object) but rather introduced by the subject, is therefore itself social” (ibid., p. 126). Segmentations of the population into clusters of consumers with homogeneous behaviors and shared values could be usefully reread or reformulated in order to identify the pertinence processes characteristic of individual social groups.

The investigation of the criteria by which the consumer actualizes some of the usage programs inscribed in the object (and not others), and of the isotopies legitimizing the syntax of purchasing and consuming different products by the same subject, might perhaps, in the future, become the value-oriented investigation par excellence: for we know that “there exists a very close, multidirectional interaction between the worldview, the way in which a culture

selects its own semantic units, and the system of meanings that name and ‘interpret’ them” (Eco, 1975, p. 116).

It thus seems to us that the analysis of a consumption behavior that tends to present itself as an appropriative/productive tactic, as a practice of “resemanticization of use-objects,” and that appears endowed with a sort of “aesthetic charge that is introduced into the functionality of the everyday” (Greimas 1987, Italian trans., p. 69), requires a critical reexamination of segmentation criteria. The study of social pertinence and resemanticization practices should also possess some predictive power. It would then be desirable to devise new classifications capable of “identifying new pertinences that can be activated in light of other reading practices” (Eco, 1990, p. 139).

It becomes clear that knowledge of the semantic fields—complementary or contradictory (Eco, 1975, p. 117)—to which a particular cultural unit may belong becomes a strategic tool not only at the level of product planning, technical features, design, or packaging, but also as a criterion for the dispositio of advertising communication. There are, in fact, numerous advertisements that demonstrate clear knowledge of the encyclopedic and ideological competencies of the addressee: so much so that the corresponding texts are arranged in a dispositio that rigorously accounts for the contradiction or complementarity of semantic spaces.

What we wish to assert is that, since “ideology itself, the subject of presupposition, is an organized worldview that can be subjected to semiotic analysis” (ibid., p. 359), the data that emerge from a possible market survey could

be organized rigorously and be immediately usable. Especially since the advertising medium is not always called upon to propose absolute positive values attributable to the promoted product: on the contrary, advertising—acting as a lever of marketing strategy—may instead undertake an “argumentative” proposal of values (that is, in opposition to previously conveyed values or to values regarded as negative). Therefore, as advertisers are well aware, it is not only a matter of conquering new market segments or creating new needs, but also of replacing axiological domains through a corrective valorization (Pozzato, 1991, p. 9).

Such replacement of axiological domains often takes the form of ideological manipulation. Consider the case of the automobile advertisements discussed in paragraph 1.4. In that case, we identified two types of contradictions that the product promotion had to reckon with: on the one hand, we find the same social and cultural system that, in a syncretic manner, both opposes and assigns the subject to a program of reunion with nature (or, more generally, with “naturalness”); on the other hand, we observed how the value of efficiency—a pertinent trait of the automobile product—may be interpreted as a disvalue when the reference parameters are those of environmental balance preservation.

It is no coincidence that we have defined the “ecological problem” as the crucial and emblematic issue of complex societies: the impression is that in the future, advertising will find it increasingly difficult to conceal the terms of this contradiction, and that marketing will have to rely on other strategic levers (first and foremost, technological product innovation) to overcome potential resistances or barriers. The recent medium- and long-term programs of Fiat and the goal of “total quality” are signs of this trend.

It is worth noting that, in contrast to the advertisements previously cited, there exists a group of car manufacturers who have chosen, and are choosing, not to conceal the automobile/environment conflict and have assigned to advertising the task of publicizing the efforts made by the company, at the level of production, to mitigate environmental impact.

Whereas in the case of commercials the contradiction is often excluded or concealed, in print advertising one more often finds argumentative structures that directly address the issue. These cases often involve a true ideological dispositio, that is, a kind of “argumentation which, while explicitly selecting one of the possible circumstantial selections of the sememe as a premise, does not make explicit that there exist other contradictory premises or apparently complementary premises that lead to a contradictory conclusion, thus concealing the contradiction of the semantic space” (Eco, 1975, p. 364).

We may hypothesize that, in cases where the consumption of a given product is recognized as potentially conflicting with shared values, the choice not to conceal the contradiction becomes strategic. In other words, a brand may position itself against its competitors precisely by acknowledging a given value conflict. The key point we wish to emphasize is that a single brand has the opportunity to position itself vis-à-vis the competition even through typically advertising-related choices: such as the type of inventio and argumentative dispositio, and the characteristics of the enunciative contract.

1.5. Advertising in the Marketing Mix

We have briefly outlined some of the fundamental functions that the marketing mix may assign to advertising communication. If the example proved useful in identifying one of the ways in which an advertising campaign can contribute to determining the positioning of a product, we must nevertheless bear in mind that advertising, as part of the levers of the marketing mix, may from time to time assume very different functions. The very group of advertisements previously considered (cf. 1.4.), which we had supposed to be homogeneous in some respects, may in fact turn out to be highly varied depending on our point of view. Two competing products, for instance, occupying different positions in the market or at different stages of their life cycle⁸, may exhibit similar strategies in terms of advertising communication, yet with a tactical significance within the overall marketing strategy that is markedly different. We must therefore distinguish the possible levels of analysis of an advertising text and always be aware of the network of relations in which it is inevitably embedded.

This does not mean that a specific analysis at the level of enunciation, for example, or the consideration and systematic organization of the “statements generated by various extra-advertising semioses (oral, visual, behavioural) currently circulating regarding the good under examination, as well as its competitors and its symbolically complementary goods” (Grandi, 1990b), do not hold value even as isolated investigations. On the contrary, as we shall attempt to explore in greater depth in the final part of our study, and as already anticipated in paragraphs 1.4 and 1.4.1, in a context such as the current one—characterized by

stagnation and saturation in certain markets—marketing necessarily assigns to communication a driving and modelling role over all other initiatives. For this reason, the ability to communicate and to anticipate existing social discourses about the product proves to be an indispensable tool.

In any case, when identifying the enunciative strategies that characterize advertising communications, it is especially useful to direct our attention to those factors that are necessarily interrelated with the tactical/strategic function of the advertising medium.

It will have been noticed that in the preceding chapters advertising communication has been discussed as though it were almost exclusively responding to a competitive strategy, and more specifically to a positioning strategy. This occurred not only due to expository requirements but also, and above all, because competitive strategies are indeed the most widespread. Nevertheless, the consideration of a typology encompassing at least the principal strategic functions that advertising may assume will help clarify the relationship that develops between the marketing strategy, the communication strategy, and the enunciative strategy.

1.5.1 Communication Strategy and Marketing Policy

Bernard Brochand and Jacques Lendrevie, in their *Le Publicitor* (1983), concisely and clearly summarize the fundamental concepts that regulate the relationship between an overall marketing policy and an advertising campaign that

aims to be “strategic.” Some of the assumptions found in their text may be subject to critique in light of the proposals discussed in the previous chapters. For now, it is sufficient to note that the vision offered by Le Publicitor concerning the relationship between marketing strategy and advertising decisions is still a hierarchical one: the communication strategy, which in this case serves a tactical function, must respond coherently to the strategic directives developed by the marketing policy. According to the two authors—or, more broadly, according to the assumptions of marketing over the past two decades—a good “communication strategy links advertising decisions to the marketing strategy. Advertising is at the service of marketing, and the communication strategy places it in its proper role. It is a factor of coherence between the marketing policy and the advertising policy. It is also a factor of cohesion among the various communication decisions.” (Brochand and Lendrevie, 1983, Italian translation, p. 51)

The statement is indisputable and offers a methodological indication that should not be taken as universally accepted: in theory, the decision-making process follows a series of rigorous and established steps, but in practice many advertising agencies still do not believe they should measure creative choices against the “cold” parameters of brand and product strategy. Moreover, many small and medium-sized Italian companies are still unable to develop a marketing strategy that is binding for the advertising campaign. The paradox is that marketing is now critically revisiting those theoretical assumptions that companies and agencies have not yet fully adopted.

In the current scenario—characterized by increasing systemic complexity, unpredictable consumer behavior, the emergence of new social actors who share

values that cut across traditional class boundaries, and saturated or stagnant markets—the relationship between marketing policy and communication strategy is destined to assume a new role within the decision-making process. If there is still a hierarchy, it now appears to be inverted: it is no longer the consumption targets identified through market research that define the communication targets, but rather communication itself, as a lever of the marketing mix, that is called upon to create communication targets from which corresponding consumption targets can be deduced. (Weil, 1986)

The procedure we are describing had already been implicitly suggested when we spoke of the need for marketing to become “tactical,” to understand the occasional, appropriative, and refunctionalizing moves that characterize consumer behavior. The importance of communication’s role in the new social context is such that “the true product communication now deals with is the company’s program, and not only to make it known and attractive, but to conceive it and give it the means to be born and to succeed.” (ibid., p. 188)

The discussion regarding the inversion of decision-making processes—which we believe will clarify the concepts expressed above—will be conducted in paragraph 2.5.

In the meantime, we reproduce in the following figure the diagram representing “the sequence of communication decisions” (Brochand and Lendrevie, 1983, Italian translation, p. 52), because, in its simplicity, it clearly illustrates the decision-making process that we will attempt to critically examine in paragraph 2.5.

If we accept this diagram (which foresees the subordination of advertising choices to the marketing policy), the relationship between communication strategy and marketing strategy can be described with a certain degree of rigor and systematization. The typology proposed in *Le Publicitor* describes, case by case, the nature of the relationships that take shape between a given type of advertising campaign and the strategic objectives pursued. It is a classification that is neither exhaustive nor highly detailed, but which nevertheless provides us with some useful basic information.

The case of promotional advertising strategies serves as a useful example for describing the marketing/communication relationship. According to the classification proposed by Brochand and Lendrevie, each advertising campaign is

distinguished from others by the objectives it is tasked with achieving; the main objectives of promotional strategies can be summarized as follows:

- to get consumers to try a product
- to foster loyalty
- to rekindle interest in a product, especially during off-peak market periods

[...]

– to energize the distribution channel, to encourage selling, display, and visibility of the product...

- to respond to a competitor's attack. (ibid., p. 61)

From reading the objectives listed above, it becomes clear that the advertising campaign is in this case called upon to fulfill a tactical function. In marketing studies, "tactic" generally refers to "the operational tool through which a strategy can be activated and implemented; it is thus something far more specific and detailed than a strategy. Generally speaking, tactics also refer to short-term actions, whereas strategy involves decisions with a longer-term validity." (Stanton and Varaldo, 1986, p. 47)

And indeed, when Brochand and Lendrevie propose a classification of strategies (cf. fig. no. 2), they refer to marketing strategies that determine what they define as "advertising strategies" but which, strictly speaking, should be defined as "tactics." Beyond a distinction that is only seemingly terminological, what we find useful to highlight is that the subordinate relationship of the communication mix to the marketing mix now appears highly questionable.

In addition to the reasons already amply discussed, we can add that if the choice of communication strategy alone can determine the product's positioning, enable absolute or corrective valorizations, and even intervene on the object's use value, then the decision-making process described in marketing textbooks could indeed be reversed: parameters such as product and price could even become operational levers available to the communication strategy.

It is conceivable that, in the near future, Weil's claim that "communication is the company's program" will become the guiding assumption regulating marketing decision-making processes—especially in markets where products appear to be homogeneous in terms of use value. The French researcher is, in fact, rather emphatic in her forecasts:

"In the end, it is no longer merely a matter of advertising a ready-made product, brand, or service, but of using communication for the very feasibility of the project—for its conception, its birth, and its success. It is by transforming a virtual project into a real one that communication truly aspires to become a tool of management. This is typically the role played by internal communication in motivating personnel: it fully participates in the realization of the company's project." (Weil, 1986, Italian translation, p. 188)

1.5.2 Communication Strategy and Enunciative Strategy

Within a marketing decision-making process that places advertising choices in a subordinate relationship to the operative decisions of marketing, the “creative”

work will consequently also be determined by the communication strategy. The very example cited in Le Publicitor is indicative in this sense; under the entry “the main competitors or enemies,” the “creative work plan” is described as follows:

“[Competitors] can be described in marketing terms or in advertising terms:

– in marketing terms, it is not a simple list of brands, but the selection of the brands against which one wishes to position oneself, after analyzing the sources of profit, the unmet desires of the target, the desired brand image, the distribution network, etc.

– in advertising terms, it is a matter of studying the language of the chosen enemies (competitive monitoring) and their media strategy in order to decide whether to speak like them, to play on confusion, or to speak differently by adopting a code that is one's own and original.”

(Brochand and Lendrevie, 1983, Italian translation, p. 205)

Clearly, issues such as “sources of profit” or the “distribution network” will still fall under the responsibility of the company's marketing department. However, it is also evident that the choice between “speaking the language of the competition” and “adopting a proprietary code” requires refined tools for evaluation and control. It is a choice, we may add, that can condition other marketing initiatives. It is therefore not merely a matter of rightly recognizing the strategic value of advertising choices; rather, it involves acknowledging the possibility that what is referred to as the “creative department” of the advertising agency may become a productive laboratory for marketing ideas.

To clarify the matter, we believe it is necessary at least to distinguish between two preliminary tools available to advertising strategy: the identification of areas of discursive competition and the selection of the communicational contract.

The identification of a ‘polemical field,’ of oppositional subsystems present within a certain semantic space, constitutes the first and fundamental step in outlining a strategic advertising plan. Since it is plausible that, in advertising discourse, “toute assertion du message est une réponse à des arguments circulant dans le discours social” (Chabrol and Charaudeau, 1989, p. 154), advertising communication ends up requiring such a level of preliminary analysis that it

becomes the true means of controlling the positioning of the product. To identify areas of discursive competition ultimately means to identify the dynamics of the market.

This obviously does not mean that certain strategic choices are removed from the domain of marketing—particularly in relation to its specific levers such as price, distribution, or the material characteristics of the product. However, in a market system where even use value itself becomes the object of advertising manipulation (cf. 1.4 and 1.4.1), it is more than acceptable for a marketing policy to begin precisely with the study of the “discourses” of the competition.

The issue presents itself differently, however, when it comes to communicational contracts and enunciative strategies. Since it is likely that there does not exist a one-to-one correspondence between each advertising objective and a specific enunciative strategy—and that therefore the same enunciative strategy may be called upon to perform very different strategic functions—its study, though indispensable, is not sufficient for the elaboration of a positioning strategy. On the other hand, the selection of a specific enunciative strategy nevertheless has considerable repercussions both on the effectiveness of argumentative processes and on the overall achievement of communication objectives.

In other words, if the same enunciative strategy can be used for communications characterized by different objectives, this does not mean that all combinations are possible.¹⁰

2. ENUNCIATIVE STRATEGIES OF COMPLICITY

2.0. Premise

In the preceding pages, we discussed the rationale for a new approach to the study of the strategic and tactical tools available to the advertising medium. It is well known that considering advertising as a marketing tool harmoniously integrated into a broader strategy is now theoretically taken for granted.

Now, since it is by no means certain that advertising agencies—assuming they do strictly subordinate creative choices to the dictates of the marketing strategy defined by the client—actually use specific tools to monitor the coherence of individual tactical decisions, a few elements emerge that warrant critical discussion. In reading recent marketing and advertising manuals, one even gets the impression that advertising choices made after the drafting of the copy strategy cannot—or should not—be guided by strategic criteria.¹¹ On the one hand, advertising is entrusted with achieving certain objectives established by the marketing strategy; on the other, no clear criteria (or means of control) are provided for the ensuing decisions.

In fact, if the copy strategy is that fundamental document “which defines the evolution of the brand in the consumer’s mind over time” (Brochand and Lendrevie, 1986, Italian trans. p.198), although it does “explain what the advertising message should be (i.e., the substance),” it offers no indication “of the specific and precise form it should take” (ibid.).

This assertion also seems contradictory in light of the claim that the copy strategy should indicate “the tone, the personality, the overall atmosphere the advertising should communicate” (ibid.), since these are variables that are intrinsically linked to the form of the advertising message. This contradiction is embedded within a context that is already quite confused: on one hand, the desire is for advertising to be ‘aware’ of the objectives assigned to it by the marketing strategy; on the other, the expectation is that the advertising agency should be equipped with strategic knowledge that addresses nearly all the parameters of marketing (while inexplicably neglecting those that are specifically advertising-related). When the copy strategy is called upon to provide precise indications regarding the very variables that should fall within its domain, it delegates the task to the agency’s “creative department,” as though choices concerning enunciative contracts or argumentative structure did not require input other than that—albeit indispensable—supplied by the copywriter’s flair and sensitivity.

We are, of course, simplifying the issue somewhat, as decisions regarding advertising—as well as those concerning a marketing policy—are organized through highly complex processes that vary considerably from case to case. Nonetheless, it is striking that a marketing logic which attributes great strategic importance to advertising would neglect the study of the specific tools that advertising can develop and employ.

The advertising world has been asked to adopt the language and mindset of marketing, to reason in terms of objectives and strategies, and to take on challenges related to segmentation and the selection of reference target groups.

And the responses, in this regard, have been satisfactory: the fact that a book like *Le Publicitor*, considered a good advertising manual, ultimately reads like a concise marketing text that devotes many pages to advertising, seems to us quite telling. However, as we mentioned, analytical tools are accepted and used to the extent that they prove capable of offering an objective to the communication strategy; when, instead, they claim to contribute to the decision-making processes traditionally left to “creativity,” the attitude of advertisers shifts significantly.

We have introduced the theme of “creativity” because it will appear more or less explicitly throughout this second part of our analysis. On the one hand, in fact, the communication strategy is a matter that inevitably raises “creative” issues; on the other, the use of semiotic tools for studying advertising communication is often met with indifference or suspicion. The reasons for this attitude have already been partially addressed; they can nevertheless be traced back to the preconceived notion that analytical tools (of any kind) represent a treacherous constraint on creativity, and to the conviction—not entirely unfounded—that the craft of advertising is, by its very nature, destined to remain asystematic.

We believe, however, that the grounds for such objections are bound to fade. First of all, it is unclear why technical refinement must necessarily entail limitations for creative processes, which, of course, can never be entirely set aside. Moreover, the idea that creativity is the exclusive instrument and property of the advertising function has no real justification: in reality, decisions made in other areas and at other stages of the marketing plan—although supported by more or less sophisticated investigative tools—are the result of abductive processes, of hypotheses whose formulation requires a considerable dose of creativity.¹²

We conclude this introduction with two brief clarifications (which are, in fact, short recaps). The first is that, as we have often hinted, our interest is specifically directed toward print advertisements (whose effectiveness is likely determined largely by the choice of communication contract and enunciative strategy, the identification of pertinent zones of discursive competition, and the selection of argumentative structure). The second, closely linked to the first, is that when we have spoken of “specific tools of advertising communication,” we have referred explicitly to communication through print advertisements. Therefore, while we previously focused on issues related to consumer behavior and advertising in general, the discussion that follows will address a seemingly narrower subject (even though we are convinced that many of the issues we will examine in relation to print ads are by no means irrelevant to other forms of advertising communication). Finally, we wish to emphasize that the following discussion aims to position itself coherently as a consequence of the argument developed in the first chapter (The Two Productions) and as a premise for the Conclusions in the final part of the thesis.

2.1. Interpretive Cooperation

We have already had the opportunity to underscore (cf. 1.4.) how the act of reading constitutes the necessary condition for textual actualization. This observation allowed us to identify some important analogies between the act of reading and the act of consumption. Both are in fact productive practices, by no means passive, characterized by tactical procedures of construction and

deconstruction that parasitically find their place of exercise within the space outlined by the textual strategy.

While we have emphasized that there are limits to interpretation set by the textual strategy itself, we have nonetheless wished to stress the possibility of appropriations (and of the subject's pertinentization of objects with respect to use value) on the part of the reader (and of the consumer) that are potentially 'subversive' with regard to the competence postulated by the text. This is not only because, in any case, "every act of reading is a difficult transaction between the competence of the reader (the knowledge of the world shared by the reader) and the kind of competence that a given text postulates in order to be read economically" (Eco, 1990, p. 110); but also, and above all, because we were interested in highlighting the polemical and contractual character of the relationship that is delineated between the strategy of the world of production and the appropriative tactics of the reader-consumer.

We must now rather consider the negotiated process described above as a sort of 'preliminary' to the occurrence of the condition necessary for the actualization of the text: this condition is the reader's cooperative activity. We must also take into account the hypothesis that advertising communication, as a circumstance of the act of reading, requires or determines a particular type of reader cooperation. Indeed, if it is well known that the same utterance can be interpreted differently depending on the circumstances of enunciation, it is likewise predictable that the degree of ambiguity of an utterance, or the occurrence of the conditions for its effectiveness, will prove sensitive to circumstantial selections.

It also seems to us that the very 'disposition' to cooperate on the part of the reader should not be considered a variable of minor importance. It is therefore not only a matter of verifying how (through which procedures) a certain enunciative strategy engages the enunciatee in that productive practice which is interpretation, but also whether the cooperative investment finds sufficient conditions for its occurrence.

Moreover, it is also possible that there exists an intensity of the reader's interpretive cooperation; if in fact we consider cooperation not only as the necessary practice for the actualization of the text, but also as the sign of a 'bond' between enunciator and enunciatee, we may understand how the latter can be more or less intensely implicated, more or less intensely involved.

The current climate of "acceptance" towards advertising should not make us forget that advertising communication "is by its very constitutional status intrusive" (Grandi, 1989, p. 63), and that it must still reckon with "the risk of being rejected or, at most, endured." (ibid., p. 65). The peculiarities of the advertising medium are thus such that the reader's cooperation itself may be considered a strategic objective of the communication: cooperative investment may, for example, contribute to overcoming the aforementioned "intrusiveness."

These considerations, in the meantime, serve as a necessary premise to the discussion of the "strategies of complicity." Since one of the objectives pursued by this class of strategies is the involvement of the addressee in interpretive processes, and since the cooperative investment itself may in turn assume a

strategic function in achieving distinct objectives, a preliminary clarification has proven necessary. We must therefore keep in mind that advertising constitutes a communicative circumstance whose analysis requires us to assume the concept of “interpretive cooperation” in a restricted sense. The statement that a strategy that uses the “involvement of the addressee” aims “to produce the effect of a ‘community’ of readers” (Bertrand, 1988, it. trans., p. 119) would otherwise risk being generic and uninformative.

Cooperative activity, which may be more or less intensely solicited and may actualize different portions of the reader’s competence, is, in the case of advertising communication, not only the necessary condition for the actualization of the text, but the sign of a complicity between enunciator and enunciatee. The strategic value of the reader’s cooperative investment lies precisely in the possibility of determining different types and degrees of complicity. It is in fact conceivable that if different texts correspond to different forms of interpretive cooperation, the latter in turn imply distinct types of complicity. The cooperation necessary to disambiguate a plurisotopic text and that required to recognize a quotation—two recurring examples in advertising discourse—though they undoubtedly share many features, are in fact two markedly different situations that involve distinct activations of the reader’s competences.

As should now be clear, the issue of the reader’s cooperative investment is of primary importance to a discussion of the “strategies of complicity” (cf. 2.3). For now, it is enough to add that the call for interpretive cooperation may entail a valorization of the enunciatee’s competence, and thus be part of a strategy of seduction. Since the valorization of the enunciatee’s competence—whether

encyclopedic or, more simply, enunciative—entails a modification of their modal competence, the possible euphoric orientations of the subject must be taken into account.

One final observation before concluding the paragraph: considering the reader as the point of convergence of the competences that characterize them makes it possible to view the communication target as an entity selectable by the textual strategy. The reader, therefore, “cannot be considered in the analysis as a ‘given,’ but rather as a ‘construction.’ He is the effect of meaning produced by the competences that construct his image.” (Bertrand, 1988, *it. trans.*, p. 121). We have seen (cf. chapter 1) that it is the very competences of the subject that determine the appropriative criteria characterizing consumption; and by “appropriation” we mean a process of pertinentization that follows criteria “introduced by the subject” (Prieto, 1975) according to their competences. The consumer—or rather, the Model Consumer—may likewise be defined as the “theoretical point of convergence of the competences that construct his image.” These considerations, we believe, have at least two important consequences.

The first is that the systematic identification of the subject’s competences proves useful both for a marketing strategy and for a communication strategy; the competences of the reader-consumer in fact govern both the pertinentization processes of objects and the interpretive cooperation processes of texts. As we said earlier, semiotics may prove to be a useful tool for marketing insofar as it can operate in synergy with other disciplines; indeed, it seems to us that knowledge of the subject’s competences can only benefit from prior market research. In this

case, then, semiotics can provide the criteria for research and, above all, organize the data obtained.

The second consequence is that if the textual strategy “constructs” a Model Reader whose competences it postulates, advertising communication can aspire not only to the selection of the target group chosen by the marketing strategy, but also to the “creation” of the communication target and, consequently, to the “prefiguration” of the consumption target (cf. chap. 3). One may understand that the possibility—even if theoretical—of creating new, presumably transversal targets with respect to traditional clusters becomes fundamentally important in those markets that show signs of growing saturation. In fact, it is the phase in which a single market finds itself that determines the role of communication with respect to the other levers of the marketing mix:

“Whereas [when the economy was in a growth phase] communication had to promote the sensitivity of existing consumption targets, the current trend [in an economic context that sees stagnation and saturation of certain markets] is to assign it a different role: by creating temporary communication targets, it must prefigure consumption targets.” (Weil, 1986, it. trans., p. 201)

2.2. Page Layout

If the text of a magazine page “is read in relation to a frame, to images, to a certain graphic layout, to a certain organization of the page’s space, all these

elements together constituting the perceived object” (Fisher and Veron, 1986, it. trans., p.144), then the text of a print advertisement likewise enters into relation with the other elements that make up the ad. Furthermore, considering that there are recurring patterns across the many forms of print advertisements, it is reasonable to hypothesize the existence of a kind of prototypical model of spatial organization of the page, which sets up a system of expectations as part of the reader’s competence. It then becomes clear that a print ad, in general, can deviate from a certain norm (and thus assume a self-reflexive function) simply by operating at the level of page layout alone. Put differently, the advertising message can display varying degrees of ambiguity to the extent that its spatial organization diverges from the structure of a hypothetical model-ad.

We have seen that disambiguation processes in any case require a certain type of competence on the part of the subject, who thus finds themselves in a position of interpretive cooperation. It is reasonable to assume that knowledge—albeit implicit and unconscious—of the hypothetical model-ad is not universally widespread. A deviation from the norm may therefore presumably assume a self-reflexive function only for limited groups of readers (which can nevertheless be of great interest to a marketing policy). What we wish to emphasize, ultimately, is that the call for cooperation directed to the reader of a print advertisement can be taken on by the very structure of the ad itself—namely, by its format.

We may further consider that such a deviation from the norm can be part of a strategy of seduction, since, by engaging the interpretive capacity of the reader, it implicitly valorizes their competence [cf. note 14]. In the specific case, we are dealing with a form of intertextual competence that includes knowledge of the

norms governing the page layout of an advertising text. We are speaking of a particular target group, probably on the rise, ideologically well-disposed toward the advertising phenomenon and attentive to its 'stylistic' evolutions. In this case, the textual strategy can hypothesize a competence of the enunciatee that also includes knowledge of what we have called the "discourses of the competition"; identifying the zones of discursive competition would, in such a communicative context, hold fundamental strategic value and facilitate the choice of the type of communicative strategy.

We may, in any case, consider deviation from the model structure of the ad as one of the many synergic moves that can assume a self-reflexive function and that, therefore, can serve as a preliminary tactic for different strategies.

The consideration of the spatial distribution of the print ad also holds relevance because each element corresponds to a distinct function. Annamaria Testa describes "the model structure of the print ad" by enumerating its constituent parts: "The elements at play are five: a visual (the image), a headline (the title), a bodycopy (the text), a baseline or payoff (the final and summarizing sentence), and a format (the general layout, including page layout and typography). To these we must add the brand and the name of the company behind the campaign." (Testa, 1988, p.52)

We must first observe that the format should not be considered homogeneous with the other components mentioned. Indeed, the definition of the format entails choices concerning the parts that make up the ad: it is the format

that decides, for example, the presence or absence of the headline or the payoff. We can say that the format is the very structure of the page.

As mentioned, the parts composing the model structure of the ad are not merely elements occupying space on the page, but also, and above all, areas assigned to specific functions. While it is relatively easy to identify the separate functions that, in theoretical terms, are normally attributed to the individual elements of the ad, it is more difficult—but also more interesting—to identify the relationships that these elements establish with one another. The definition of the headline as “the opening phrase that generally summarizes the central theme of the campaign or the individual ad” (The Dictionary of Advertising and Communication, 1988, p.142), tells us little about the actual functions it may assume within the context of the ad. Of particular interest to us is the relationship that this element may establish with the bodycopy. Here too we are forced to generalize: there are in fact a vast number of variants. Nevertheless, we may assert that, generally speaking, the headline is particularly apt to perform an attentional function, whereas the bodycopy is often the place assigned to argumentation. As we will verify in subsequent analyses, it sometimes happens that an ambiguous or ironic utterance placed in the position of the headline is followed by an extended bodycopy which provides isotopic markers of reading that guide the reader in the disambiguation of the entire ad (cf. 2.4.1). When we examine some of the possible enunciative strategies capable of “producing complicity,” we will thus try to consider the relationships among the components of the ad. We will also seek to hypothesize and verify whether the organization of the ad’s elements—its page layout—can function as a device producing effects of meaning such as, for instance, temporality and aspectuality. The example we have proposed, regarding

the relationship between headline and bodycopy, already seems to highlight a configuration of the aspectual type: the reading of the ad thus presents itself as a process that is active and voluntary, but which may nonetheless be guided—also at this level—by the textual strategy.

2.3. Veridiction and Fiduciary Convention

When we turned our attention to the productive aspects of consumption and reading (chapter 1), our aim was not, as we have repeatedly stated, to place the consumer and the reader in a privileged position of “free will” with respect to the textual strategy. In fact, we simultaneously highlighted the constraints that the textual strategy imposes on the act of reading and pertinence-setting. The intention was rather to emphasize the interactional nature of meaning production. Indeed, the “conclusions” we will propose in the final chapter will rest on a foundational assumption, namely that the “strategy” of the world of production and the “appropriative tactics” of the consumer and reader are the players in a game of exchanges, shifts, and resistances, the outcomes of which neither side can fully predict.

This assumption aligns with relatively recent theoretical developments in the field of marketing and mass communication studies:

“The recipient of mass communication took years to be recognized as a communicative subject who is in some way active. This trajectory recalls the

parallel and in some ways analogous journey of the consumer, initially a target to be bombarded, then a subject with needs to be met.” (Grandi, 1987, p. 31)

The very idea that among the objectives of advertising communication there may be that of “creating complicity” seems to us an implicit recognition of the recipient as an active participant in communication.

As an introduction to the theme of “strategies of complicity,” we deem it necessary to briefly address the issue of the truthfulness of advertising discourse. As we shall see, the strategic decision to pursue the implication and involvement of the recipient as the goal of communication is, in many ways, linked to this issue. If any discourse is “the fragile place in which truth and falsehood, lies and secrecy are inscribed and read” (Greimas, 1983, It. trans., p. 103), the issue must necessarily concern advertising discourse as well. The latter, moreover, does not allow for the establishment of enunciative contracts based on what Greimas calls evidence (Greimas and Courtés, 1979, It. trans., p. 137), since there is certainly no collective epistemic stance a priori oriented toward a veridictive interpretation of advertising discourse. [cf. note 15]

The production of the truth effect, analogously to the processes of pertinence-setting and textual actualization, results from an interactional process. The modes of veridiction we mentioned (truth, falsehood, lie, secret) result in fact “from the dual contribution of the enunciator and the enunciatee. Their various positions are fixed only in the form of a more or less stable equilibrium that stems from an implicit agreement between the two actants of the communication structure” (ibid.).

In Greimasian semiotics, where the problem of “truth” is replaced by that of telling-the-truth (*dire-vrai*), the agreement between enunciator and enunciatee — “this tacit understanding of two more or less conscious accomplices” (Greimas and Courtés, 1979, *It. trans.*, p. 380) — is called a veridiction contract.

The veridiction contract “tends to establish a fiduciary convention between the enunciator and the enunciatee, a convention that concerns the veridictive status (the telling-the-truth) of the discourse-enunciation” (*ibid.*, p. 81). Since, as we mentioned, it cannot be based in advertising on evidence, the veridiction contract must be preceded by a persuasive act (*making-believe*) on the part of the enunciator. This persuasive act corresponds to an interpretative act by the enunciatee that leads to an epistemic judgment (*i.e.*, a belief). Therefore, the effectiveness of the persuasive act depends on the sanction of the enunciatee.

According to Greimasian semiotics, the enunciative contract itself appears as a convention that concerns the veridictive status of the enunciation and therefore must also be preceded by a persuasive act. The point to be evaluated — and we consider it highly important — is whether the effectiveness of advertising discourse necessarily depends on its veridictive status. Even when the persuasive procedure takes an argumentative form, its effectiveness does not necessarily depend on the recipient’s recognition of its “truth” as adequate to some referential reality.

It is thus necessary to formulate some hypotheses regarding the collective epistemic stance toward advertising communication — not because we are currently in a position to say something definitive, but because we believe that

some choice, however intuitive or arbitrary, is indispensable to proceed with the discussion. Our hypothesis is therefore as follows: that advertising is the site of discourses which are not collectively expected to carry a veridictive status. Not only that: we believe that the epistemic attitude toward advertising discourse is, in many respects, quite varied. We hypothesize that the recipient grants the enunciator legitimacy in their telling-the-truth when the persuasive effort concerns certain issues, and not others.

Let us now present a brief example to clarify the above. A recent print ad for the new Audi 100 features three distinct enunciations. In the headline, we read:

“New Audi 100. Those who saw it were speechless. Those who drove it are still talking about it.”

Then, in the lower part of the page, in uppercase and with a significantly smaller font size than the headline, we find the following:

“New Audi 100: 2000 cc, 85 kW (115 hp) – 2200 cc, 169 kW (230 hp) – 2500 cc TDI, 85 kW (115 hp) – 2800 cc, 128 kW (174 hp). Standard catalyzation on all models.”

Without dwelling on the differing levels of ambiguity between the two statements and the different kinds of competence activated in the interpretive cooperation process – note, however, that the second statement seems to value a rather specific encyclopedic competence – our goal here is to formulate hypotheses about the epistemic stance toward advertising truth-telling.

We believe that the first statement does not “require,” as a condition of acceptability, to be read as “true,” whereas the second is acceptable only insofar as it is “true.” We are not speaking of truth as correspondence to an external reality, nor even as correspondence to the cognitive universe of the enunciatee (cf. Greimas, 1983); we are specifically interested in the attitudes and expectations toward advertising veridiction.

We believe that the enunciatee – presumed to recognize advertising as a circumstantial mode of enunciation – does not assume that the first statement must be true: they know it could be true, but also that it is not even the enunciator’s intent to make them believe it. The expectations surrounding the second statement (a typical occurrence of advertising that lists “technical features” of the product) are intuitively very different. In this case, the enunciatee has no reason to doubt its truthfulness; in fact, they consider it adequate to a reality

external to the enunciation and, above all, do not attribute any manipulative intent to the enunciator.

In other words, while the enunciatee legitimizes the enunciator in claiming that “those who saw the new Audi 100 were speechless” — while admitting the possibility that the statement may not be true — the same enunciatee accepts the second statement as true because they believe the enunciator could not say otherwise. In the first case, the enunciatee allows the enunciator to violate Grice’s second maxim of quality: “Do not say that for which you lack adequate evidence” (Grice, 1967, *It. trans.*, p. 205). However, the same tolerance does not seem to apply, in general, to violations of the first maxim of quality: “Do not say what you believe to be false” (*ibid.*).

The third enunciation in the ad is the payoff next to the “Audi” logo: “At the forefront of technology.” This statement, clearly referring to the brand rather than the specific model being promoted, raises some questions about its veridictive status. It is, in this sense, quite different from the other two. It resembles the first in that the enunciatee does not assume a priori that it is true; however, there is a key difference: in this case, the enunciatee attributes to the enunciator a veridictive strategy — a desire to be believed — which they did not attribute to the headline.

The enunciatee is thus entitled to sanction the statement. Given that the manipulative intent recognized by the enunciatee is, on the other hand, legitimized by the advertising context — advertising is openly manipulative — it seems unlikely that the enunciatee’s epistemic act will amount to categorical recognition of correspondence to their cognitive universe. Rather, as already partially emerged in

the case of the headline, the enunciatee seems to decide between believing more or believing less, rather than between believing and not believing.

Obviously, our considerations are arbitrary, as they rest on conjectures about the recipient's expectations concerning the truthfulness of advertising discourse. Nevertheless, we are convinced that it is crucial – especially for describing the objectives of complicity strategies – to take into account the structural nature of epistemic modalities, which are gradual and not categorical. As Greimas says: “Certainty, the supreme sanction to which truthful discourse must submit, is a relative and gradual concept, and belief is a fragile thing.” (ibid., p. 110)

The enunciator's persuasive act and the enunciatee's interpretative act must, in any case, be considered preliminary cognitive operations for establishing the enunciative contract, which is the necessary condition for communication. And the contract, “though based on the results of cognitive work, is not itself cognitive in nature, but fiduciary” (ibid., p. 109).

Assuming, therefore, that the truthfulness of advertising discourse affects its effectiveness to some extent, we must nevertheless consider that “truth is an object of communication and requires fiduciary sanction” (ibid.).

Our hypothesis is that the advertising enunciation context generates a system of expectations on the part of the enunciatee, such that the enunciative contract itself (of a fiduciary nature) requires specific conditions for its implementation. As we have seen, presumably the advertising enunciative contract does not necessarily pertain to the veridictive status of the enunciation. The fiduciary

convention that enables advertising communication appears, then, as something rather “subtle,” an “unstable” condition whose implementation requires not so much a preliminary making-believe by the enunciator (and a believing by the enunciatee), but more likely a persuasive effort that values the recipient’s knowledge.

We have already emphasized how the cooperative implication of the reader — the construction of a “complicit” enunciatee actively involved in text interpretation — entails a valorization of the reader’s competence (cf. 2.1. and 2.2.). So much so that this cooperative investment, insofar as it stimulates the reader’s interpretive abilities, can serve as a tactical move in a seduction strategy.

Based on the previous discussion, we can say that the conditions for implementing the advertising fiduciary contract may be established through a seductive kind of persuasion, aimed at “constructing a complicit-enunciator.” That is, through what we call a strategy of complicity.

We report here some reflections by Denis Bertrand on the Black & White advertising campaign, which he analyzed in a relatively recent article (Bertrand, 1988), as they reiterate some of the concepts we have just discussed. The author notes how the advertising campaign in question “does not at all attempt to illustrate a product (the advertisements do not mention the product, except for the phrase ‘Scotch whisky’); nor, contrary to appearances, does it attempt to illustrate the brand and its institutional role (Black & White). Rather, it clearly highlights the elements of a specific intersubjective relationship, in which the brand’s enunciation functions as a mediator. Through this strategy, the campaign seeks to construct

complicity or connivance (or ‘tacit understanding’) based on an ironic mode of participation, which involves the enunciatee and tends to produce the effect of a ‘community’ of readers. No attempt to inform or persuade, but rather the organization of a process of self-persuasion. [...] By working directly on the partners of the communication act, this type of message displays and amplifies the usual, yet often forgotten, goal of every advertising discourse: to invite the addressee to become a co-enunciator (or accomplice-enunciator).” (Bertrand, 1988, Ital. trans., p. 119)

However, it should be noted that the achievement of the goal to “invite the addressee to become a co-enunciator” does not necessarily imply that the advertising campaign “does not mention the product,” nor that arguments aimed at its valorization are absent. On the contrary, it is plausible that a strategy of complicity may also be required to establish the preliminary conditions for other types of enunciative strategies, or for argumentative discursive strategies. Furthermore, our assumption that the advertising fiduciary contract does not necessarily bear on the veridictory status of the discourse does not authorize the exclusion of the possibility that advertising communication may also use contracts of veridiction. The example we have offered (the print advertisement for the New Audi 100) rather demonstrates that within the same ad, there may coexist different types of possible agreements between enunciator and enunciatee regarding the veridictory status of individual utterances. The description of the product’s “technical features,” especially when it does not involve implicit comparison with competing products, appears not only to tend toward veridiction, but also encounters a predisposition on the part of the recipient to believe. On the other

hand, in the case of the headline of the advertisement, it seemed to us that the effect of the “truth” meaning was not even among the goals of the textual strategy.

Advertising communication is thus an extremely complex phenomenon that involves a multitude of enunciative and discursive strategies—and thus communication contracts—not easily classifiable. It is also very likely that different epistemic attitudes exist with respect to the type of product advertised; indeed, it is reasonable to assume that a pharmaceutical product advertisement may, to some extent, prompt the enunciatee to attribute a strategy of veridiction to the enunciator. Such an attribution is intuitively less likely in the case of clothing advertisements, for instance. Although we do not delve into this specific issue here, we mention it in order to emphasize the complexity of the problem and to encourage further analysis.

To our hypothesis that the fiduciary convention does not necessarily concern the veridictory status of the advertising utterance-discourse, one might object that numerous advertisements do indeed show the inscription of veridictional markers. This objection is only partially valid. First, we must keep in mind that the inscription of veridictional markers generates a veridictory dispositif which, “even while ensuring a certain discursive coherence at this level, does not in any way guarantee the transmission of truth, which depends exclusively on the epistemic mechanisms installed at both ends of the communication chain, within the instances of enunciator and enunciatee—or rather, on the proper coordination of these mechanisms. [...] The enunciator may well claim, regarding the object of knowledge being communicated, that they ‘know it,’ that it is ‘certain,’ that it is ‘evident’; this in no way ensures that they will be believed by the enunciatee: a

believing-true must be installed at both ends of the communication channel.”
(Greimas & Courtés, 1979, p. 380)

In other words, only the addressee’s adherence can validate the contract of veridiction. Recent print advertisements for dermatological products, in fact, uniformly exhibit the use of the type of manipulation that Greimas defines as objectifying disguise (Greimas, 1983). This type of communication, typical of scientific discourse, “in order to be accepted as true, seeks to appear not as the discourse of a subject but as the pure utterance of the necessary relationships between things. For this reason, it erases enunciation marks as much as possible.”
(Greimas, 1983, p. 108)

Dissolvere le rughe è un sogno.
Combatterle, un dovere.

Biovytena Dermon.
Una vera barriera attiva contro le rughe.

Biovytena Demon è un sistema di tre formulazioni, da combinare secondo l'età, per modulare l'efficacia.

Biovytena Demon è a base di Bvretin-E, il complesso esclusivo Demon, il cui effetto biodinamico è assicurato dalla presenza di precursori biologici per veicolare le sostanze attive fino alla struttura vitale della pelle.

FLUIDO ANTIRUGHE PER IL GIORNO.
Contro l'invecchiamento cutaneo e le aggressioni dell'ambiente.
È una crema fluida che equilibra la perdita di elasticità, ridà tono all'epidermide e ne aumenta la capacità di idratazione.
Ottimizza, con una notevole azione antiradicalica, l'attività funzionale del tessuto cutaneo, contribuendo ad una significativa azione contro le rughe.

CREMA MICROSTRUTTURATA ANTIRUGHE PER LA NOTTE.
Per ripristinare nel sonno lo stato ideale di equilibrio della pelle.
Studiata specificamente per rafforzare l'azione antirughe della Crema Fluida per il Giorno, durante il sonno, quando cioè l'organismo è più ricettivo, ricostituisce l'equilibrio biologico dell'epidermide.
Svolge una profonda azione nutriente contro tutti i tipi di rughe, anche quelle più pronunciate.

TRATTAMENTO D'URTO ANTIRUGHE IN PERLE.
Anche nei casi estremi con la forza d'urto di un concentrato
È una formula speciale, così ricca di principi attivi da riequilibrare rapidamente le funzioni cutanee e il rinnovamento cellulare.
Il Trattamento d'Urto può essere utilizzato sistematicamente, per un'azione sostanziale contro le rughe più profonde, oppure saltuariamente, per combattere affaticamento e stress.

Let us consider an excerpt from the body copy of the Biovytena Dermon ad:

“[...] Biovytena Dermon contains Byretin-E, the exclusive Dermon complex, whose biodynamic effect is ensured by the presence of biological precursors to deliver active ingredients to the skin’s vital structure.”

Here we note the elimination of the enunciating subject, and the presupposition of an “it is true that...” whose function, as is well known, is “to modalize the utterance according to objectivity.” (ibid.) We nonetheless believe—and this is the key point we wish to emphasize—that even if such a veridictory *dispositif* corresponds to a cognitive adherence by the recipient, the strategy of objectifying disguise must be assessed, in the specific context of advertising enunciation, from different perspectives. In our view, even in the case of a strategy aimed at seeming-true, what is more relevant is the type of involvement and complicity, the degree to which the enunciatee’s competence is valorized, rather than their epistemic sanction. The hypothesis is that the strategic power of objectifying disguise lies not so much in the production of a “truth” effect of meaning, but rather in the distancing of the enunciatee. As Andrea Semprini has pointed out regarding the strategies found in sales catalogs (Semprini, 1990), the distancing of the enunciatee does not result in their devaluation. On the contrary, this kind of contract proposition posits an enunciator who, “by not addressing any specific enunciatee, leaves the latter free to adhere—or not—to the propositions” (Semprini, 1990, p. 195); it is a strategy that ultimately enhances the addressee’s autonomy of judgment, allowing them to affirm “their simulacrum of pragmatic and cognitive autonomy” (ibid.).

We are thus dealing with a type of strategy that ideally contrasts with that of complicity. Nonetheless, even this strategy, insofar as it valorizes the enunciatee at the level of “autonomy of judgment,” may be included among the strategies of seduction and appears capable of creating the conditions for the establishment of a fiduciary contract.

Here, then, we identify a complicity/distancing dichotomy, which we believe can account for a portion of contemporary advertising strategies. The present analysis is especially concerned with the strategies of complicity; however, we must remember that the opposition between complicity and distancing is not categorical but gradual. A strategy can thus appear more or less “complicit” and more or less “distancing.” Below, we will schematically summarize the main characteristics of the two types of strategy, before proceeding to the discussion of the specific ways in which complicity strategies may be implemented. It should be noted that some concepts present in the schema, such as the “creation of actantial syncretisms,” will be discussed in the following paragraph.

2.4 Strategies of Complicity

Paragraphs 2.1 and 2.2, dedicated to the reader’s cooperation in interpreting texts and to the self-referential function that decisions related to the format can confer on an advertisement, have already anticipated some of the ways in which a strategy of complicity is implemented. Whether the reader collaborates in the actualization of the text or recognizes violations of the hypothetical prototype structure of the advertisement (cf. 2.2), they activate specific portions of their own

COMPLICITY STRATEGIES

creation of actantial
syncretisms:
narrator/narratee

enunciative contract
that does not
necessarily entail
the veridictive statute
of the enunciation

strong implication of
the receiver in
interpretative processes

heightened valorization
of the competence
of the receiver:
seduction
(which does not entail
a devaluation of
the enunciator)

Orientation of the receiver
endowed with a knowing
how to do
toward a euphoric situation

DISTANCING STRATEGIES

possible cancellation
of marks of
enunciation
(objectifying masking)

enunciative contract
that may entail
the veridictive statute
of the enunciation

heightened valorization
of the competence
of the enunciator
(which does not entail
a devaluation of
the receiver)

Orientation of the receiver
endowed with
a knowing how *not to do*
toward a euphoric situation
(valorization of prag-
matic and cognitive
autonomy)

competence. Thus, one fundamental characteristic of the strategy of complicity is that it aims, among other things, at the cooperative investment of the reader.

What remains to be seen is through which enunciative and discursive procedures—and, more broadly, through which communicative tactics—advertising seeks to achieve this goal. The following paragraphs will focus mainly on two tactics of invoking interpretative cooperation that we consider particularly significant within the context of advertising (2.4.1 The Ambiguous Statement – 2.4.2 Actantial Syncretisms). We will discuss the use of the ambiguous, plurisotopic utterance—an utterance that calls for ‘active’ and, so to speak, ironic disambiguation by the reader (2.4.1).

Strategies of complicity, whose aim is precisely to create “complicity”—a term, as we have seen, not devoid of nuances and which we will attempt to summarize and discuss in paragraph 2.4.2—find their conditions of implementation not only through the reader’s cooperative investment, but also through the construction of actantial syncretisms between narrator and narratee. This issue will be addressed and clarified in paragraph 2.4.2.

2.4.1 The Ambiguous Statement

We define ambiguity as “the property of statements that simultaneously present multiple possible readings or interpretations (with none prevailing over the others)” (Greimas & Courtés, 1979, Eng. trans. p.30). Natural language contains numerous types of ambiguity: lexical, functional, morphological, syntactic, and others (cf. Aissen and Hankamer, 1977). Since our aim here is not to classify the types of ambiguity found in advertising discourse, we shall focus on a single advertisement that serves as an illustrative example.

The advertisement in question promotes Canon fax machines (cf. fig. 4). Let us focus on the headline:

“Dritto a destinazione” [“Straight to its destination”].

This phrase appears at the top left of the page, next to a photographic image showing a steamroller about to run over a row of paper sheets (about the size of letter paper), each partially rolled up. Below, another photographic image—slightly larger than the headline itself—shows an object that at first glance might be interpreted as either a photocopier or a fax machine. To understand that it is in fact a fax machine, it suffices for the reader to spot the “Canon” logo at the bottom of the page, accompanied by the word “fax,” prominently displayed. Beneath the two images is a fairly extended body copy.

The phrase “Dritto a destinazione,” when decontextualized, does not appear to be highly ambiguous. However, it becomes ambiguous in light of the broader context—that is, the images and texts composing the ad. Let us first examine the virtual ambiguity of the statement while ignoring the photographic images. The word *dritto* can be read in at least two ways: as an adverb (“directly”) or as an adjective (“straight” as opposed to curved). Do the surrounding co-textual elements determine one or the other reading?

An encyclopedic representation (Eco, 1975; 1979) of *destinazione* (“destination”) includes several contextual selections, the most relevant being “a travel destination” and “the place something is sent to.” Both of these activate an

isotopy of “travel or trajectory.” This isotopy, however, does not decide the interpretation of *dritto*: it could still be read either as referring to the path of an object (adverb) or to its physical state (adjective). Thus, at least two legitimate readings coexist.

Turning now to the visual elements of the ad: the two main components of the image next to the headline (the steamroller and the partially rolled-up sheets of paper) do not resolve the ambiguity. The presence of the steamroller, as a vehicle in motion, appears to activate the adverbial reading of *dritto* (“directly to...”). But within the encyclopedic representation of steamroller, one also finds its functional purpose: to transform surfaces—rough to smooth, curved to flat, etc. Thus, the image of the curved paper sheets can equally legitimize an adjectival reading of *dritto*, as referring to the resulting straightened state of the paper.

However, since the identification of the relevant isotopy is a matter of abductive reasoning, the two legitimate readings cannot be assumed to be equally accessible. Intertextual scripts (Eco, 1979) may guide the reader toward favoring one isotopy over another. While there are no well-established intertextual scripts concerning the “physical distortion of documents during transmission,” the expression “*arrivare dritti a destinazione*” [“go straight to the destination”] is a common Italian idiom, generally meaning “to arrive directly at the intended place.” Thus, the reader’s abductive effort is differently distributed depending on the reading.

The other photographic image (that of the fax machine), together with the logo at the bottom, clarifies that the product is a fax machine. Yet this does not

eliminate the dual reading of the headline. After all, the act of sending paper documents does not inherently resolve whether dritto refers to the object's path or its final condition.

Only the body copy clarifies the intended reading. Its first two sentences read:

“A Canon plain-paper fax always arrives straight to its destination. Plain paper, unlike thermal paper, does not curl.”

Dritto a destinazione.

Un fax Canon a carta comune arriva sempre dritto a destinazione. La carta comune, infatti, al contrario della carta termica, non si arrotola.

PPF Ma non solo: i modelli Canon PPF (Plain Paper Fax) vi danno documenti facili da leggere, da evidenziare, da archiviare, da ritrasmettere. Non c'è da sorprendersi se i fax Canon sono il numero uno in Europa*. Ma c'è un altro fatto importante che fa di Canon un leader:

la sua tecnologia esclusiva di elaborazione dell'immagine UHQ (Ultra High Quality).

UHQ Con il sistema UHQ potete trasmettere con la massima fedeltà anche documenti composti da immagini e testo. Per quanto complesso sia il vostro documento, avrete sempre la sicurezza di un risultato pari all'originale. Ma Canon non si limita ad offrirvi i fax a carta comune e il sistema UHQ: mette a disposizione anche una vastissima scelta di soluzioni che va dai modelli ad alte prestazioni, come il potente fax laser, ai fax per uso personale. Ma controllate di persona: richiedete il materiale informativo. Canon... arriva dritto al vostro problema, e lo risolve.

Canon FAX

81ann1.cresci1.com

Per maggiori informazioni sui fax Canon

Nome: _____ Indirizzo: _____
 Azienda: _____ Cap: _____ Città: _____

Inviare questo coupon in busta chiusa a: Canon Italia S.p.A., Divisione Facsimile, Via Mercurio 90, 20118 Milano oppure telefonare al numero 02-5092278.

The second sentence here disambiguates the first, confirming that *dritto* functions adverbially—referring to the directness of delivery. Note, however, that the first sentence is itself lexically ambiguous: the term *fax* can denote either the machine or the document sent. The expression “plain-paper fax” reduces this ambiguity, implying a reference to the machine.

Finally, a metalinguistic statement concludes the body copy:

“Canon... goes straight to your problem—and solves it.”

This last statement again activates *dritto* as an adverb and serves to ‘legitimize’ the dual reading of the headline. The enunciator, who remains implicit in the text, here speaks indirectly about his own enunciation—revealing his discursive strategy. It is as if the text were confirming that both readings are not only possible but anticipated within the advertising strategy.

Translator’s Notes

In Italian, the word dritto can function both as an adverb (“directly, straight to...”) and an adjective (“straight” as opposed to bent or curled). This double reading is essential to the layered meaning of the headline Dritto a destinazione. The visual cue of a steamroller straightening curled sheets hints at the adjective (not bent), while the idiomatic meaning of the phrase suggests the adverbial reading (directly to the recipient). The ambiguity thus invites the reader into a playful interpretive task.

This type of lexical ambiguity—activated by both linguistic and visual contexts—is particularly productive in advertising, especially in languages like Italian that allow such dual readings within a

single form (dritto). The English translation “straight to its destination” preserves the adverbial reading, but loses the adjective-related pun unless explained.

The second example is taken from a promotional advertisement—specifically, one of those whose goal is “to highlight and enhance special promotional initiatives” (Brochand & Lendrevie, 1983, Eng. trans. p.61). The ad comes from the Italian weekly *L'Espresso* and is intended to inform readers that, starting with the following issue, the magazine will include a cassette tape featuring Mozart's music and a series of articles and reports on his work, over the course of four weeks.

The headline is divided into two segments, split by the visual (an image of a Mozart cassette tape). The first part, “Il genio è compreso” [“The genius is included”], clearly plays on the reversal of the well-known trope “un genio incompreso” (“a misunderstood genius”), while the second part, “Dentro *L'Espresso*” [“Inside *L'Espresso*”], makes the first part ambiguous.

Indeed, the second segment exerts a co-textual pressure on the first without resolving the ambiguity of the term *compreso*. Two readings become equally plausible due to the context: one, where *compreso* means “understood”, and another, where it means “included”. Thus, the phrase “Il genio è compreso dentro *L'Espresso*” can be interpreted in two ways: either as “*L'Espresso* has understood the genius [of Mozart]” and wishes to convey that understanding to the reader, or as “The genius [i.e., Mozart's work] is physically included inside *L'Espresso* [the magazine].”

Il genio è compreso.

Dentro L'Espresso.

I. Le Sinfonie.

A partire da lunedì prossimo, per quattro settimane consecutive, L'Espresso pubblicherà articoli, inchieste e servizi su Mozart, la sua vita, le sue opere, il suo genio creativo.

Per farvi conoscere davvero Mozart, L'Espresso ve lo farà anche ascoltare regalandovi 4 musicassette con tutto il meglio del repertorio mozartiano. Ecco il programma: *I. Le Sinfonie*, Selezione dalle Sinfonie n. 35, n. 36 e n. 38 interpretate dalla Wiener Philhar-

moniker diretta da James Levine, *II. I Concerti*, Interpretati dalla Orpheus Chamber Orchestra e dalla London Symphony Orchestra, diretta da Claudio Abbado, *III. La Musica da Camera*, Interpretata da Maria Joao Pires, Itzhak Perlman, Daniel Barenboim e dall'Hagen Quartett.

IV. Le Opere, Interpretate dalla Wiener Philharmoniker e dalla Berliner Philharmoniker dirette da Karl Böhm.

L'Espresso

Le musicassette di Mozart sono prodotte dalla Deutsche Grammophon, e sono incise su nastri al cromo: tutto per garantirvi la massima qualità nell'ascolto.

In ogni musicassetta c'è anche la "Mozart 3D Card" della Deutsche Grammophon: l'unica carta di credito con la quale potrete acquistare l'intera "Mozart 3D Collection" ad un prezzo davvero speciale.

La prossima settimana in regalo la prima musicassetta di Mozart.

The body copy does not offer any definitive disambiguation of the headline. Its first two paragraphs read:

"Starting next Monday, for four consecutive weeks, L'Espresso will publish articles, investigations, and reports about Mozart—his life, his work, and his creative genius. And to let you really get to know Mozart, L'Espresso will also let you listen to him, offering four cassette tapes with the best of his repertoire."

Both isotopies of the headline are thus validated: the ad aims to tell the potential buyer that the magazine offers the opportunity to understand (through the articles) and to receive (through the tape) Mozart's genius. What interests us particularly is the ironic character of the headline: the playful cooperation invited by the reversal of the common saying "a misunderstood genius" and the dual activation of two distinct meanings of the sememe |compreso|.

Translator's Notes

The Italian word compreso means both "understood" and "included". The headline "Il genio è compreso" thus generates a pun: on one level, it implies that Mozart's genius is understood by the magazine's editorial staff (and thus, potentially, by the reader); on another, that the genius (his music) is included as a physical supplement (cassette tape). English lacks a single term that carries both senses simultaneously, so the ambiguity must be conveyed through explanation.

The irony relies on a reversal of the Italian cultural topos "genio incompreso" (the misunderstood genius), transforming it into "genio compreso." This subversion creates a clever effect: it suggests that L'Espresso not only values Mozart but also makes him accessible. The use of this phrase in an advertisement balances informational content and playful tone, inviting the reader to participate in the decoding of its layered message.

The second advertisement we examine also calls upon the reader for a cooperative, complicit, and ironic interpretation. The advertisement in question is for Zerowatt's Spaziozero 33. Once again, the key components are the headline, the visual, and the body copy (which includes a bolded sentence that stands out

from the rest). As with the other examples we have analyzed, this ad leverages the ambiguity of statements to elicit the reader's cooperative engagement.

The headline statement ("Depth record: 33 centimeters") clearly lends itself to at least two distinct readings. The first, legitimized by the presence of two pairs of diving fins in the visual, activates for the term *profondità* ("depth") the contextual meaning of "verticality": the relevant isotopy would then be "underwater immersion." In this reading, the statement relies on a logical figure of paradox: it defies common sense that one might set a record for underwater depth by reaching only 33 centimeters. Of course, we are not claiming that the enunciator genuinely intends this reading. Rather, the enunciator is inviting the enunciatee to recognize the possibility of such a reading, and that recognition yields both a general ironic and playful effect, and a dual valorization—of the discursive competence of the enunciator and the interpretive competence of the enunciatee.

Already the isolated sentence from the body copy—written in uppercase, bolded, in a larger font, underlined, and visually distinct—"A large washing machine only 33 centimeters deep") performs a first and fundamental disambiguation of the headline: the topic is not underwater diving, but rather the dimensions of a washing machine. The following sentence ("The slimmest washing machine in the world definitively solves all your space problems") then definitively clarifies the headline. The term *slim* exerts a co-textual pressure that activates for depth the meaning of "horizontal compactness" rather than vertical dimension.

It is also noteworthy that the part of the ad detailing the appliance's technical features ("*Variable capacity from 1 to 4 kg. *18 programs *'No Iron' button *Steel

generazione design '91

RECORD DI PROFONDITÀ: 33 CENTIMETRI

Zerowatt Spaziozero 33 ha battuto ogni record

UNA GRANDE LAVATRICE PROFONDA SOLO 33 CENTIMETRI

La lavatrice più sottile del mondo dà un taglio definitivo a tutti i problemi di spazio. Bastano 33 centimetri di casa tua per avere tutta l'alta tecnologia Zerowatt:

- Capacità variabile da 1 a 4 kg.
- 18 programmi
- Tasto non stiro
- Vasca e cesto in acciaio inox

Zerowatt Spaziozero 33: qualità che si apprezzano con un'occhiata e qualità che si scoprono con tanti anni di fedelissimi e perfetti bucati.

giannicresci.com

ZEROWATT SPAZIOZero 33

tub and drum”) activates specific portions of the reader’s encyclopedic competence. Since these features are listed without further clarification, we must assume that the enunciator is addressing a reader capable of recognizing their value. This last statement, we could say, performs a triple valorization: of the functional qualities of the product, of the enunciator’s competence (who shows an understanding of the reader’s assumed needs), and of the reader’s encyclopedic competence (in a form of seduction: the reader is endowed with a “can-do” capability).

Another mechanism used in advertising to call upon the reader's interpretive cooperation is citation. And at times, citation can also carry a generally ironic tone. Consider the advertisement for the New Philishave 975. The headline reads:

"New Philishave 975. All your beard, minute by minute."

This clearly references the famous Italian radio program *Tutto il calcio minuto per minuto* ("All the football, minute by minute"), which broadcasts live commentary on Serie A soccer matches.

Translator's note

The humor and cultural reference here depend on a pun involving the phrase "minute by minute." In the original Italian context, this phrase is synonymous with detailed, real-time coverage of football games. The advertisement plays on this well-known formula to humorously suggest that the razor provides an equally precise and attentive shave.

Moreover, the first part of the body copy mimics the enunciative style of a sports commentary broadcast:

"Philishave 975 enters the field with the exclusive 'Minute Left' function, and your shave wins the match."

PHILIPS

**NUOVO PHILISHAVE 975.
TUTTA LA BARBA MINUTO PER MINUTO.**

PHILISHAVE
975

40
20

CHARGE CONTROL

PHILIPS

Extra in campo Philishave 975 con l'esclusiva funzione "Minutes Left" e la vostra rasatura vince la partita. Infatti "Minutes Left" vi segnala esattamente, sul display a cristalli liquidi, quanti minuti di rasatura senza fili avete ancora a disposizione prima che le batterie si scarichino. Ma niente paura: Philishave 975, come tutti i nuovi modelli Philishave, si ricarica completamente in mezz'ora soltanto, ha le nuove testine per una rasatura a doppia azione ancora più profonda e il nuovo tagliabasette. Non perdetevi altri minuti preziosi, provatelo.

giannicresci.com

The ad thus uses the citation, on one hand, to target a specific type of reader and to encourage a playful, interpretive cooperation, and on the other, to highlight a technical feature of the product: “In fact, ‘Minute Left’ tells you exactly, via an LCD display, how many minutes of cordless shaving you have available [...]”. The text concludes with yet another use of the term “minute”: no longer referring to those lost waiting for the razor to recharge, but instead to those between reading the ad and possibly purchasing the product: “Don’t lose another precious minute—try it.”

2.4.2. Actantial Syncretisms

We define “strategies of complicity” not only as those characterized by the cooperative investment of the reader (cf. §§ 2.1 and 2.4.1) and the valorization of their competencies, but also as those that present syncretisms between narrator and narratee, i.e., between the simulacra of the enunciator and enunciatee constructed within the text. As we have seen (§ 2.3), some advertising messages tend to erase enunciative markers. We have associated such messages with a set of strategies termed “distancing strategies,” which can be ideologically opposed to the class of “strategies of complicity” (see fig. 3). The latter are generally characterized by a more clearly delineated narratee, who sometimes becomes syncretized with the narrator.

The discussion of two print advertisements from recent publications will clarify the concepts just outlined. It is worth prefacing that the first example was not chosen because it neatly confirms our hypotheses; on the contrary, we found it useful to focus on an advertisement that poses some classification difficulties. In fact, advertisements rarely present a homogeneous enunciative mechanism across all their parts: for instance, a bodycopy shaped by complicity between narrator and narratee may be accompanied by a headline that presents a sharp separation between the two enunciative simulacra. Likewise, a playful, ambiguous headline may coexist with a bodycopy that, through erasure of enunciative marks, adheres to a veridictive regime. Even the Canon fax advertisement—previously considered an example of a complicity strategy—displays a tendency in its bodycopy to modalize statements according to objectivity (Greimas 1983, It. trans. p.108). It is therefore necessary to identify the overall strategy of the advertisement, and to

treat its component parts as distinct factors whose interaction determines the communicative effect. For instance, the aim underlying the complicity strategy in the Canon fax advertisement is, after all, to inform potential consumers of the product's technical features. In this case, the ambiguity of the headline (and of the advertisement as a whole) becomes a tactical tool for "leading" the reader into the bodycopy.

The next example we examine is an advertisement for o.b. tampons. The headline reads as follows:

"I want protection that makes me feel free."

"Voglio una protezione che mi faccia sentire libera."

Per noi donne, durante il ciclo è importante non avere interferenze nelle attività quotidiane. Gli assorbenti esterni, così scomodi e ingombranti, non sono sempre l'ideale. Vogliamo parlarvi di un tipo di protezione diversa, più comoda e discreta. Provala: non l'abbandonerai più. Si chiama o.b. ideato da una ginecologa, è usato da decine di milioni di donne in Europa. I tamponi o.b. rispettano il naturale decorso del flusso e, variando di spessore, eliminano ogni possibilità di fuoriuscite. Sono il modo più comodo e sicuro per affrontare il nostro ciclo. o.b. è disponibile in varie misure: o.b. mini, o.b. normale e o.b. super, ideale per i flussi più intensi. o.b. è la scelta di vivere quei giorni come tutti gli altri giorni. È non è questo in fondo quello che abbiamo sempre desiderato?

o.b.
normal
20 Assorbenti esterni

o.k.o.b.

Se preferisci ricevere maggiori informazioni ed un campione gratis, al costo di un solo scatto, il numero verde è 800400111 e funziona nelle ore d'ufficio. Copiare questo spazio tagliando.

Nome e Cognome _____
 Via _____
 Cap _____ Città _____
 Spedite a: Servizio Clienti o.b. - Laura Sereni
Johnson & Johnson S.p.A.
 Via della Pace 35 - 00040 Pomezia (Roma)

This is a rather unusual—though not unprecedented—case of an enunciatee inserted into the text via direct speech, through their simulacrum, that is, the narratee. The “I” (here implied), which is typically the “I” of the narrator constructed by the enunciator, is in this case that of the narratee. This inversion of enunciative roles is immediately evident thanks to two explicit cues marking the presence of the narratee: the use of italics (here presented as handwriting), and quotation marks.

Let us now consider the bodycopy. The text reads:

“For us women, during our period it is important not to have disruptions in our daily activities. External pads, so bulky and uncomfortable, are not always ideal. We want to tell you about a different kind of protection, more comfortable and discreet. Try it: you’ll never go back. It’s called o.b.: created by a gynecologist, it’s used by tens of millions of women across Europe. o.b. tampons respect the natural course of the flow and, by varying in thickness, eliminate any risk of leakage. They are the most comfortable and secure way to go through our cycle. o.b. comes in various sizes: o.b. mini, o.b. regular, and o.b. super, ideal for heavier flows. o.b. is the choice to live those days like any other day. And isn’t that, after all, what we’ve always wanted?”

The first thing to note is that the typographic shift and removal of quotation marks indicate a clear break between this enunciation (the bodycopy) and the preceding one (the headline). This observation supports our initial hypothesis: that the “I” of the headline is that of the narratee.

A second observation concerns the use, in the opening sentence, of an inclusive “we” (“we women”) which casts the narrator’s role in syncretism with that of the narratee. This first sentence of the bodycopy (“For us women, during our period...”) legitimates, as it were, the desire attributed to the enunciatee in the headline: the desire is legitimate because it is shared by a group of people that includes both narrator and narratee. It would thus appear that this “we” constitutes a truly collective actant, a syncretic actant “within which the actantial roles of narrator and narratee coexist in a state of relative indifferentiation” (Semprini, 1990, p.190).

Yet the third sentence of the bodycopy (“We want to tell you about a different kind of protection...”) invites a significantly different interpretation. The “we women” appears now as a collective actant not in syncretism with the narratee; here, the enunciation clearly establishes a distance between narrator and narratee, with each assigned a distinct role. The enunciator, therefore, while embedding a dialogue in the text between a narrator and a narratee who share the same needs and desires, also maintains a clear distinction between them and affirms the narrator’s competence by authorizing them to issue validations and to modalize the narratee.

As we can see, this advertisement is not easily classifiable. It features a strongly marked presence of the enunciatee (through their simulacrum), indicative of a complicity-oriented strategy; yet it also seeks to valorize the narrator’s expertise. As previously stated, identifying the overarching strategy of the advertisement should help frame its components within a coherent schema. We

believe the communicative strategy here is to create an “intermediary subject” positioned between the consumer’s potential demand and the product’s performance. This intermediary must, for credibility, be a woman; must appear complicit (sharing the enunciatee’s problems and desires); and must be competent (able to understand those problems and propose solutions). Given these aims, the advertisement’s dual strategy—simultaneously of complicity and of distancing—is no longer a sign of inconsistency. It generates an effect of complicity through the inscription of the enunciatee via their simulacrum (the narratee), and through temporary use of the inclusive “we,” while simultaneously affirming the narrator’s competence by distinguishing their actantial roles from the narratee’s.

PENSIAMO A NOI STESSI SENZA CIRCOLI VIZIOSI.

GLANNICRESCT.COM

Sentiamo sul nostro corpo i nodi di una tensione che non si scioglie facilmente. Muscoli e nervi rispondono così agli equilibrismi che dobbiamo sostenere ogni giorno. Questa matassa di attività ordinarie e straordinarie che dobbiamo svolgere ingarbuglia e confonde i nostri desideri. Per ritrovare il filo diretto con noi stessi, ci sono le Terme. Dove la nostra ricerca di armonia e benessere si nutre di luce, di verde e di incontri con gli altri. Dove cure antiche, la cui efficacia terapeutica è oggi ampiamente riconosciuta - prima di tutto le acque da bere e poi i vapori, i fanghi - permettono un nuovo equilibrio con il nostro corpo. Un equilibrio libero.

A S S O T E R M E . D O V E R I T R O V A R S I .

A CURA DELLE AZIENDE TERMALI A PARTECIPAZIONE STATALE. Acqui, Salice, Merano, Recoaro, Salsomaggiore, Castrocaro, Montecatini, Casciana, Chianciano, Stabiane, (Castellammare di Stabia), Agnano, S. Cesarea, Sibarite (Cassano Jonio).

We now briefly turn to an advertisement that poses fewer classification challenges: the full-page advertisement for Assoterme, which fully exhibits the features of a strategy of complicity. We have identified such strategies by the presence of ambiguous utterances that invite playful, ironic, and cooperative readings, as well as by enunciative mechanisms that place the narrator in syncretism with the narratee. The ad's format itself, which does not immediately reveal the promoted product or service, adopts a reflexive function, and the only image (a contortionist) does not clarify the headline's meaning ("We think about ourselves without vicious circles") so much as it solicits a playful, generally ironic reading of it.

We shall not linger here on the contextual selections of the sememes in the utterance. We believe the ad's strategy does not rely on disambiguating a bi-isotopic utterance, but rather on the hyperbolic effect produced by the interaction of visual and verbal elements. The bodycopy's first three sentences are especially significant:

"We feel the knots of a tension in our bodies that is not easily released. Muscles and nerves respond to the balancing acts we must perform every day. This tangle of ordinary and extraordinary tasks that we must perform confuses and muddles our desires."

In isolation, the utterance is not particularly ambiguous, though its emphatic tone and terms such as "knots," "release," "balancing acts," "tangle," and "muddle" may lead the reader to "suspect" some ulterior allusion. It is the contextualization

through the visual (a contortionist) that produces the hyperbolic and ironic effect. Note that hyperbole often possesses “a comic character that highlights the disproportion between words and reality [...] or the ironic detachment with which the author describes implausible feats” (Marchese, 1984, p.153). Were we to replace the image of the contortionist with, say, a tired man after a long workday, the effect would be drastically altered. We would no longer have the same ironic detachment or comic register; indeed, without the contortionist, the bodycopy’s text might appear overly emphatic and less credible.

Thus, the textual strategy of the advertisement selects a reader prepared to engage in a playful and complicit reading of the relations between visual, bodycopy, and headline. The bodycopy also reflects a consistent enunciative strategy aimed at constructing a complicit enunciatee. The entire utterance is taken up by a collective actant formed by the syncretism of narrator and narratee. Consider the second half of the text:

“To reconnect with ourselves, there are the Spas. Where our pursuit of harmony and wellness is nourished by light, by nature, and by encounters with others. Where ancient therapies—whose effectiveness is now widely recognized, beginning with drinking waters and followed by steam and mud treatments—enable a new equilibrium with our bodies. A free equilibrium.”

Unlike the o.b. advertisement, here narrator and narratee not only share the same problems and needs but are fully installed syncretically in the enunciation.

We should note, however, that this second part of the bodycopy may also authorize a different reading of the ad. Phrases such as “our pursuit of harmony” or “a new equilibrium with our bodies” may actualize virtual traits in the visual such as “Eastern disciplines” or “harmony.” In this alternative interpretation, the ironic distancing effect would fade, though the reader’s cooperative investment—and thus the complicity effect—would remain. We believe these two readings do not necessarily exclude each other, and that their concurrent legitimacy does not diminish the advertisement’s effectiveness. In fact, the ad might be said to exploit both reading levels in order to construct and select two distinct reader profiles.

From the analyses conducted in the last two sections, a few general considerations emerge. First, we have seen that very different types of advertisements can be grouped under the umbrella of “strategies of complicity,” and that there are at least two distinct ways to construct “a complicit enunciatee.” One way is to involve the reader in the text’s interpretation through a cooperative invitation that both solicits and valorizes their competencies, and invites their active, playful participation in the communicative “game.” This is a particularly “subtle” form of involvement, since the reader is not inscribed in the text through a simulacrum, and thus participates in actualizing the text only to the extent that the textual strategy successfully anticipates their competencies. This is why we have repeatedly emphasized (in §§ 2.1 and 2.4.1) that in the context of advertising, the term “cooperation” must be used in a specific sense. If we adhere to the general definition of cooperation as a necessary condition for any textual actualization, the term loses its ability to distinguish between different advertising strategies, which is precisely what we have aimed to do. We must therefore assume that

reader cooperation admits degrees, and that in certain cases—like those discussed—it may assume a playful and broadly ironic nature.

Our view is that advertising messages should be labeled “complicit” not when they demand generic interpretive cooperation, but only when that cooperation involves the reader’s strongly active and playful engagement. The examples we examined also highlighted that the reader’s cooperation may operate not only in disambiguating bi-isotopic utterances, but also—and above all—in the active “search” within the page for linguistic and visual cues that reveal the enunciator’s wit. Very often—as seen in the cases discussed—it is the interaction among an ad’s parts that generates overlapping legitimate readings, produces ironic and distancing effects, and ultimately leads the reader through a complex process to the ad’s final disambiguation. Yet—and this is the key point—the effectiveness of this type of advertisement does not reside in guiding the reader toward the “correct” isotopy, but rather in the reader’s presumably amused recognition of the multiplicity of possible readings.

As with all non-categorical and thus gradable concepts, the notion of “complicity” cannot be given a rigid definition. Still, we believe we have drawn its contours with relative precision. However, the term’s etymology may help us articulate a more accurate definition. The word “complice” derives from the Latin *complex*, *-icis*, a blend of *complicare* and *simplex*, meaning “one who folds together,” “one involved in something,” or “a companion in games or pranks.” This form of involvement, as shown in this very section, may also be realized through the creation of a collective actant in which the enunciator’s and enunciatee’s simulacra—the narrator and narratee—coexist in syncretism. It is a form of

involvement quite distinct from the one generated through the reader's cooperative implication in interpretive processes. In this case, complicity is not implicitly determined as the result of interactive activity; rather, it is "represented," explicitly declared by the text itself.

In conclusion, we wish to reiterate an important finding discussed in previous pages: the two types of complicity strategies can coexist, within the same advertisement, with markedly different or even opposing enunciative strategies. The examples we have proposed demonstrate that the strategy of complicity may serve a tactical function within a broader communicative strategy.

2.5. From Tactics to Strategy

We have repeatedly emphasized the possibility and the appropriateness of revisiting the dominant criterion in marketing theory which assigns to advertising the role of achieving objectives established by the marketing strategy. We have discussed (in sections 1.3, 1.4.1, 1.5.1, 1.5.2, 2.0) the reasons why it is legitimate to suppose that the decision-making process in marketing may usefully be configured in phases whose temporal concatenation appears, in some respects, to invert the traditional scheme of the "sequence of communication decisions" (cf. figure 1). It is now necessary to further examine the topic previously discussed and, in a sense, to relativize certain assertions that we had simplified for expository purposes. In particular, we wish to emphasize that, although it is possible to argue — for reasons we have extensively elaborated — that the marketing decision-making process may be delineated starting from typically advertising-based choices, such

an observation does not legitimize a complete reversal of the perspective that places communication-related choices in a subordinate position to the overall marketing policy.

There are, in particular, two authors — whose positions were discussed in section 1.3 — who, albeit from rather different perspectives, have recently argued for inverting the traditional marketing decision-making process: Pascale Weil and Al Ries. We have referred several times to Pascale Weil and her *Et moi, et moi* (1986). Her position can be summarized in the attribution to communication of a fundamentally leading role with respect to the other variables in marketing.

The French researcher argues that the current social structure has rendered entirely inadequate the model of a “pyramidal society” (Weil 1986, Italian trans., p. 51), in which “communication proposes as models the behaviors of the superior class” (*ibid.*). She opposes this model with what she terms a “psycho-matrix society,” whose characteristics partially overlap with those attributed to “complex” and “post-industrial” societies (a topic we discussed in sections 1.1 and 1.2):

“The social profile has become more rounded due to the increase in middle and, in part, upper classes.

- High-end markets are expanding to a new potential clientele.
- The reduction of differences between socio-professional categories.
- Increased dispersion of income within each socio-professional category.
- An overlapping of social categories.” (*ibid.*)

At the level of communication, this new scenario implies new perspectives and criteria:

“Communication touches a dimension of individuals that, on this occasion, forms a psychological consumption target. The order of the phases is reversed, communication prefigures consumption. We are witnessing the extension of a process that already exists:

- when a new product concept is invented around which demand is formalized;
- when one attempts to attract — around an existing product — new targets with motivations different from those of the original clientele.” (ibid., p. 189)

Even more explicit is the position of Al Ries, who in his *Bottom-Up Marketing* (1989), co-written with Jack Trout, presents the case for a “reverse marketing” approach that, by inverting the traditional (top-down) decision-making process, places the identification of the tactic as the initial fundamental move in defining an effective marketing plan:

“To what extent is the idea that strategy must precede tactics ingrained in the minds of marketing professionals? First of all, no one ever says ‘tactic and strategy’ but always the other way around. And the reverse seems logical: first I decide what I want to do (the strategy) and then I decide how to do it (the tactic).” (Ries & Trout 1989, Italian trans., p. 14)

Clearly, bottom-up marketing aspires to reverse what has become a consolidated and seemingly “logical” process: for the authors, in fact, it is best to start from a working tactic, and only then identify the appropriate strategy. The top-down process criticized in the book is the one exemplified in figure 1. We had already discussed in previous sections the difficulty of applying such a scheme in today’s social context, which is characterized, among other things, by elusive consumption behavior, seen as the production of personal and scarcely predictable meaning.

Without repeating discussions already held in earlier pages, it is nonetheless useful to add a clarification concerning the frequently mentioned “inversion of the marketing decision-making process.” We have highlighted how the study of “discourses of the competition,” the identification of “zones of discursive competition,” the selection of a particular reader through the proposal of a communication contract, and the potential intervention of advertising media in the very usage program of the promoted object, can today assume a strategic role of considerable importance. Since these are tools traditionally under the ‘competence’ of communication (as part of the marketing mix), it has been possible to hypothesize that this variable might claim to serve as the first step in the formulation of an overall marketing plan. However — and this is the point we wish to emphasize — it seems obvious that once the communication variables mentioned above have been determined, and once the other variables (e.g., price or distribution channel) have been coherently adjusted, the resulting marketing plan takes on the traditional appearance of the scheme presented in figure 1. If, indeed, the observational standpoints we have mentioned — and which we regard as fundamental — have suggested a certain tactic and, consequently, a particular

strategy, the latter must then resume responsibility for the other levers and assign them specific objectives to achieve. In other words, if the most effective criterion for defining a marketing strategy is under discussion, what does not appear questionable is the requirement that strategy represent a coherent design capable of assigning objectives to the available means. We thus believe that the observations of Al Ries and Pascale Weil are of significant interest insofar as they concern the decision-making process that leads to the conception of a marketing plan; this plan, however — regardless of its genesis — must still present itself as a set of hierarchical operations.

The parameters useful for conceiving an advertising strategy may therefore aspire to serve as the parameters for the overall marketing strategy itself; at this stage, the process is undoubtedly inverted. But once the marketing strategy has been established, the function of advertising communication must undergo appropriate adjustments and once again take its place as one of the available tactical levers.

Conclusions

In the first part of our analysis, we considered it useful to describe the main characteristics of what is referred to as the “Post-industrial Transition.” These characteristics—primarily linked to the emergence of new types of social aggregation that elude classifications based solely on sociodemographic parameters—appear to motivate certain shifts in perspective that marketing has undertaken in recent years. The issue, of course, primarily concerns the valid

criteria for segmenting an undifferentiated audience into communication and consumption target groups: we therefore focused on this particularly significant point.

However, since our intent was to identify the reasons behind the usefulness of a semiotic study of advertising communication, we also examined the repercussions that the systemic transformations described have had on consumer behavior itself. Our aim was not only to verify the characteristics of such behavior in societies marked by increasing systemic complexity, but above all to seek points of analogy between consumption—understood as an appropriative and sense-producing process—and the processes involved in reading an advertisement. The analogies between these two acts—consumption and reading—seem to have emerged with a certain clarity throughout our discussion. First, we observed that the attention directed toward the addressee in semiotic analysis could be compared to the (not always adequate, it must be said) attention marketing gives to consumer behavior. On one hand, semiotics recognizes in the act of reading a relatively arbitrary move: certainly constrained by isotopic reading markers, yet still productive of meaning and indispensable for the actualization of the text. On the other, marketing is, as it were, forced to take into account the productive aspects of the act of consumption, which seems to manifest as a personal and appropriative move enacted by a subject who refunctionalizes available products, assigning them functional values that are sometimes unexpected.

Moreover, just as textual strategy operates as a sort of anticipation of the reader's set of competences, marketing must act similarly: it must understand the competences of the consumer, foresee their appropriative moves, and monitor, as

much as possible, their choices of pertinence. Marketing, as is well known, has at its disposal a series of strategic levers suitable for such control; we focused in particular on one of its privileged levers: advertising. If, as we have sought to demonstrate, advertising communication is characterized by a play of moves, predictions, deviations, and resistances that exhibits certain commonalities with the interaction that takes shape between the world of production and that of consumers, then it is also possible to hypothesize that the preliminary study leading to “effective communication” constitutes a strategic moment of great importance for the marketing policy as a whole. Advertising communication would then assume not only a tactical value within a marketing strategy, but also serve as a privileged vantage point for making motivated strategic choices.

Every product is in fact inserted into “zones of discursive competition,” the identification and exploitation of which find their natural place precisely in the design and implementation of advertising communication. From these premises, we examined a series of advertisements. Our attention was mainly directed toward communicative mechanisms that seemed relatively independent from the strategic objectives taken on by the ad. The discussion of what we have termed “strategies of complicity” did not, in fact, entail defining a set of advertising strategies characterized by the same goals to be achieved. It must first be stated that the search for “complicity”—the attempt to construct an active addressee in the reading process, ludically engaged in the actualization of the text—appears to be a tactically coherent move in a context where the advertising phenomenon has reached considerable proportions and is marked by increasing “intrusiveness.” It is also worth emphasizing that the strategies of complicity—as we have thoroughly discussed—precisely because they seem to renounce veridictory mechanisms,

appear to acknowledge the characteristics of advertising communication as a particular enunciative circumstance. On the other hand, our analysis of individual advertisements has shown that the parts composing the ad often obey markedly different, and sometimes even conflicting, enunciative mechanisms.

This observation has led us to believe that the strategies aimed at creating complicity with the reader generally assume a tactical value. An advertisement that, for example, establishes a syncretism between narrator and narratee may simultaneously show a tendency to rely on the veridictory status of statements or be characterized by the use of arguments directly aimed at enhancing the promoted product's value. We thus believe we can state that there are distinct conditions for the effectiveness of an advertisement, and that such conditions are determined by strategic choices that operate synergistically yet possess different characteristics. While the analysis of the enunciative mechanisms in print advertising can usefully account for the ways in which preliminary conditions for effective communication are created, it cannot, in our view, provide sufficient elements for a classification of advertising strategies based on the objectives they aim to achieve. In other words, a single enunciative strategy may correspond to widely different overall communication strategies. Conversely, two competing products with similar functional characteristics conveyed through the same argumentative procedures may be differentiated precisely by the type of enunciative strategy employed. Thus, while it is true that competition among products takes place primarily at the level of discursive competition zones, argumentative choices, and the engagement with—or even the “creation” of—counter-arguments through presupposition (cf. note 16), it is equally true that the

choice of enunciative strategy can have determining consequences on the overall effectiveness of the communication.

NOTES

1. A similar direction seems to be taken by Paolo Mancini's article "Ancora sulla tele-enunciazione politica – Destinatari e complessità sociale", which contains a discursive analysis of an appearance on *Tribuna Politica* by a representative of the Italian Communist Party. The issue identified by Mancini is that of stratification (in this case of addressees), as previously discussed. The author emphasizes how today there are "numerous areas of intersection between sociologists and semioticians: one of these can certainly be the analysis of television discourse (...)" (Mancini, 1985, p. 165). He specifies that the aim of his article "is to analyze, through semiotic and micro-sociological tools, some indicators of social complexity," thereby recognizing the necessity—also shared by advertising communication—"to select specific addressees within the undifferentiated audience of mass communication" (ibid.). We too are attempting, albeit with different methods and parameters from those used by Mancini, to link issues such as enunciative stratification and target selection to the broader problem of social complexity.

2. One is reminded of the amusing yet legitimate remarks made by Gian Paolo Ceserani regarding certain "trends," typical of the middle class, that seemed

difficult to explain using the parameters typically inspired by the Frankfurt School and then unanimously accepted by the intellectual left. Ceserani imagines a car trip along “a provincial road in Italy” and describes the striking scenario encountered: “in front of each small villa, at the foot or edge of the wall, a series of patches of color (red, blue, yellow, green) caught our attention. What are they? They are garden gnomes: tall or short, made of terracotta or plastic, with or without Snow White, often interspersed with geranium vases or fake cement stumps hosting roses (...) Miles and miles of silver pines, thousands upon thousands of gnomes: we are undoubtedly facing a real mass consumption phenomenon; but—this is the question the advertiser would ask—who ‘launched’ these products? Where do these trends come from? (...) Who created these consumption patterns?” (Ceserani, 1975, pp. 3–4). The answer Ceserani proposes to this ‘problem’ posed by consumption behaviors is particularly interesting: “The consumer society, what we have begun to call the Receiving Society, is now capable of producing its own needs and consumption.” (ibid., p. 5). If we overlook a perhaps outdated terminology and the understandable desire to shake off a ‘sense of guilt’ that Ceserani, as a copywriter, could not avoid in a cultural paradigm that saw the advertiser as the hidden persuader in service of capitalist power, we cannot help but recognize the relevance of his position—one that is not far from the vision of consumption proposed here.

3. The passages from Umberto Eco’s article (1986) that we quoted are now revisited and developed in the author’s later book (Eco, 1990).

4. The analysis of car sector advertising in this paragraph reworks the contribution published in BERNI Stefano, CAMERANO Antonio, CRESCI Gianni, “La natura e l’oggetto magico,” *Il Ponte*, Vol. XLVII, No. 4, Vallecchi Editore, 1991

5. Jean-Marie Floch has proposed and applied, in numerous attempts to use semiotic tools for marketing issues (Floch, 1990), a structure of four types of values—PRACTICAL (utilitarian values, use values), UTOPIAN (existential or foundational values), CRITICAL (non-existential values), and PLAYFUL (non-utilitarian values)—arranged on the semiotic square (Greimas and Courtés, 1979):

- PRACTICAL > Utilitarian values (use values)
- UTOPIAN > Existential values (foundational values)
- CRITICAL > Non-existential values
- PLAYFUL > Non-utilitarian values

As Floch himself notes, “utopian” here “does not mean illusory, but rather ‘final purpose’. Narrative semiotics calls the ‘utopian space’ the space where the hero attains victory, the place where feats and the subject’s conjunctions with their core values are fulfilled” (Floch, 1987, p. 54).

6. “In Italian marketing-advertising language, the plus of a product refers to the specific features, advantages, or ‘extra qualities’ that distinguish a product from similar ones.” (Mariani and Cortese, 1988, p. 220). The benefit, by

contrast, is the “advantage of a product promised by advertising, a plus that drives the consumer to purchase.” (ibid., p. 34).

7. “The marketing mix is the combination of controllable marketing variables that a firm uses to achieve the forecasted sales volume within the target market.” (Kotler, 1967, It. trans. p. 86). “At time t , the marketing mix of a specific product can be represented by the vector $(P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4)_t$, where

P_1 = product quality,

P_2 = price,

P_3 = point of sale,

P_4 = promotion.” (ibid., p. 87).

Managing the “product” variable “means designing and developing the right products and/or services for the target market. This implies strategies to modify existing products, add new ones, and continuously assess the adequacy of the assortment. Strategic decisions are also required regarding branding, packaging, and other product characteristics.” (Stanton and Varaldo, 1964, It. trans. p. 51).

8. “Sales potential and product profitability change over time. The product life cycle is an attempt to recognize distinct phases in a product’s sales history. Depending on these phases, different opportunities and problems can be defined regarding marketing strategy and profit potential.” (Kotler, 1967, It. trans. p. 86)

9. The term communication mix refers to the set of tools such as: advertising, sales promotions, merchandising, direct marketing, public relations, propaganda, sponsorship. It is evident that the tools available to the communication mix “are multiple and combinable in different ways, even though, generally, each has fairly defined characteristics and application domains.” (Stanton and Varaldo, 1964, It. trans. p. 51). Even though in this instance we are

referring to communication as the set of available levers, our focus is clearly directed particularly toward advertising.

10. As discussed in sections 2.4., 2.4.1., and 2.4.2., many advertisements use, in their separate parts, enunciative strategies that are markedly different and sometimes even seemingly contradictory. Yet these enunciative strategies are typically subordinated to a comprehensive communication strategy. Thus, the enunciative strategy often assumes a tactical role.

11. By copy strategy, we mean “the document that summarizes and formalizes the strategic choices made to achieve communication objectives.” (Gogna, 1988, p. 86). We also clarify that by this term we do not refer to a specific advertising style. Rather, we are interested in the copy strategy’s general function as an organization of available information, serving as a preliminary phase for creative choices.

12. On the relationship between creativity (inventiveness) and abduction, see Bonfantini (1986).

13. This topic will be revisited at the end of section 2.4.2.

14. We use the term seduction in the sense proposed by Greimas. By seduction we refer to a persuasive act grounded in knowledge. This persuasive act is defined by the judgment (positive or negative) the manipulator expresses regarding the modal competence of the addressee: “When the manipulator persuades the addressee through knowledge: on the cognitive axis, he thus informs him of his judgment regarding the addressee’s competence in the form of positive or negative evaluations.” (Greimas and Courtés, 1979, It. trans. p. 207). If the judgment is negative, the manipulative act is defined as temptation; if the judgment is positive, it is called seduction. The manipulator’s persuasive action corresponds to the addressee’s interpretive action: “The addressee is led to engage

in an interpretive act and to choose necessarily [...] between two images of their competence—positive in the case of seduction, negative in the case of provocation.” (ibid.)

In the case of interpretive cooperation, the reader’s competence is implicitly valued, though not explicitly asserted by the enunciator. We are referring here to texts that strongly invite cooperative reader involvement in disambiguation. For this final point, see the conclusion of section 2.4.2.

15. “A particular form of certainty—which is the name of the positive pole of the epistemic modal category—evidence does not require the exercise of interpretive action.” (Greimas and Courtés, 1979, It. trans. p. 137). When the enunciator “engages in a persuasive act (i.e., a make-believe act), the addressee, in turn, complements this with an epistemic judgment” (ibid., p. 127). Greimas also identifies an “epistemic modal structure” and proposes the formulation of the epistemic modal category:

certainty (believe-being) – improbability (believe-not-being) – probability (not believe-not-being) – uncertainty (not believe-being).

Certainty, syntactically defined as believe-being, differs from evidence in that it presupposes an interpretive act by the addressee. We hypothesize that advertising cannot be believed—assuming, for now, that belief is even relevant— independently of the addressee’s interpretive action. Greimas’s remarks on the “problematic of epistemic competence” are particularly significant: “The epistemic judgment does not depend solely on the value of the interpretive act that precedes it [...], but also—though to a still undetermined degree—on the subject’s willingness and ability to believe.” (ibid.) For this reason, in section 2.3 we consider collective epistemic attitudes toward advertising discourse. Clearly, the discussion can at best yield only tentative suppositions; especially since “the epistemic category only comprises gradual and relative oppositions, allowing for the manifestation of many intermediate positions.” (ibid.)

16. The enunciated content does not possess the same features as the example cited by Eco in *Lector in fabula* (1979): “Carlo makes love to his wife twice a week. So does Luigi,” whose ambiguity is so striking that “even the most naïve reader cannot help but smile.” (Eco, 1979, p. 89). The difference lies not so much in the undeniably comic tone of the second sentence, but rather in the fact that the possible simultaneous readings of the headline in question do not emerge with the same immediacy.

17. We have assumed (see sections 1.4., 1.4.1., 1.5.2.) that knowledge of complementary and contradictory semantic fields (Eco, 1975, p. 117), and the identification of discursive competition zones, together with the selection of an enunciative strategy, constitute the most appropriate tools for designing a strategic advertising plan. In earlier sections, we have attempted analyses of the enunciative strategies employed by advertising discourse. These analyses reveal that enunciative strategies often take on a tactical value relative to a broader

communicative strategy. However, the fact that a given advertisement seeks a complicity-based relationship with the reader—and that the strategy is often seduction-oriented (see 2.1 and 2.3)—does not preclude the possibility that the advertisement may also employ argumentative strategies in one or more of its components.

18. We wish to highlight several issues related to presupposition. First, the strategic importance that the use of implicature can assume in advertising discourse: “The use of implicature enables the speaker to suggest, insinuate, or imply something to the addressee, without explicitly assuming direct responsibility for it. It is the receiver of the message who infers these implicit meanings, which the speaker—though having suggested them—can always deny.” (Violi and Manetti, 1979, p. 146).

Since implicature is tied to the encyclopedic and contextual knowledge of the interlocutors, to a set of assumptions the sender shares (or believes to share) with the recipient (*ibid.*, p. 147), one can see how presupposition plays a strategic role in audience selection and the implicit valorization of the reader’s competence.

Furthermore, it is important to stress that presupposition is not merely a prerequisite to be satisfied, a felicity condition for the enunciation:

“To consider presuppositions only as preconditions to be satisfied means ignoring their ability to create a new context. It is reductive to view the relationship between word and context as unidirectional.” (Eco, 1990, p. 282).

Advertising discourse can thus use presupposition not only to anticipate and assume the possible “counter-arguments” of the recipient—by identifying zones of discursive competition (see 1.4.1 and 1.5.2)—but also to create new contexts, to presuppose, and thus shape, new counter-arguments. Consider the Canon Fax ad recently discussed: the body copy “presupposes” that the reader knows (and

shares) the annoyance of a fax machine that tends to “curl up.” In this case, one may hypothesize that the advertisement, through presupposition, seeks to create a discursive competition zone useful for argumentation and for highlighting the technical advantages of the promoted product.

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